

D1.1 AutoMoTIF PLAYGROUND AND VISION

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	
Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
5G	5 th Generation Mobil Network
ABS	Automated Berthing System
AGC	Automated Gantry Crane
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ALV	Automated Lifting Vehicle
AMR	Autonomous Mobil Robot
AMS	Automatic Mooring Systems
APS	Automatic Positioning System
ARC	Automated Robot Crane
ARTG	Automated Rubber Tyred Gantry Crane
AS/RS	Automated Storage and Retrieval System
ASC	Automated Straddle Carriers
ATO	Automated Train Operation
AutoSC	Automatic Stacking Crane
AWT	Autonomous Wagon Train
BAS	Berth Allocation System
CAS	Chassis Alignment System
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
DAC	Digital Automatic Coupling
DITS	Development & Innovation in Transport Systems
DPS	Dynamic Positioning System
DSP	Data and System Planning
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
ENX	Eurnex
ERRIF	European Rail Research and Innovation Forum
ETA	Estimated time of arrival
ETD	Estimated time of departure

GoA	Grade of Automation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HU	Handling unit
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LEO	Low-Earth Orbit
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
MFT	Multimodal Freight Transport
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
PMS	Port Management System
PCS	Port Community Systems
PortCDM	Port Collaborative Decision Making
RFI	Rete Ferroviaria Italiana
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
Ro-Ro	Roll-on/Roll-off
RSSB	Rail Safety and Standards Board
RTG	Rubber Tyred Gantry Crane
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SSS	Short sea shipping
STS	Ship-To-Shore
TIMS	Train Integrity Monitoring System
TLC	Terminal Logic Control Interface
TMS	Traffic Management System
TOS	Terminal Operating System
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
UIC	International Union of Railways
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure Communication
V2P	Vehicle-to-People Communication
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle Communication
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything Communication
VHF	Very High Frequency
VTS	Vessel Traffic System

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1 Executive Summary

The AutoMoTIF project aims to revolutionize multimodal freight transport through the integration of automation technologies, enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of logistics operations. As global supply chains become increasingly complex and demands for rapid delivery escalate, the need for innovative solutions in freight transport has never been more critical.

This deliverable, **D1.1 - AutoMoTIF Playground and Vision**, outlines the project's framework and its commitment to developing automated solutions tailored for multimodal terminals. The document details four specific use cases, including automated berthing/unberthing of vessels, automated port operations, automated shunting as a service, and automated multimodal terminal operations. Each use case is analysed to identify user needs, technological gaps, and current technological solutions, scenarios and Concept of Operations, establishing a comprehensive understanding of the operational landscape. Finally, an Open Reference Architecture for Smart Digital Twins in logistics is proposed, serving as a flexible framework that will be tailored to meet the specific requirements of each use case in WP2.

Key findings indicate that stakeholders in the logistics sector prioritize efficiency, safety, reliability, and sustainability in their operations. The project recognizes these user needs and addresses the technological gaps that currently impede optimal performance, such as automation limitations, interoperability issues, and insufficient data integration capabilities. By leveraging advanced technologies such as automated guided vehicles (AGVs), real-time monitoring systems, and predictive analytics, the AutoMoTIF project aims to create a more agile and responsive multimodal transport network. Furthermore, the document includes relevant case studies that showcase successful implementations of automation in various ports and terminals, providing valuable insights into best practices and lessons learned.

Finally, the document introduces the description of four Use Cases, which exemplify the project's vision and approach:

UC1. Automated Berthing/Unberthing of Freight Vessels: Simulates the automation of the port call process, from vessel arrival to departure, including tugboat assignment and docking operations.

UC2. Automated Port Operations: Demonstrates in Port of Bilbao the impact of automating key terminal processes, such as cargo handling, ro-ro terminals, warehouse operations, and vehicle flows.

UC3. Automated Shunting as a Service-Oriented Platform: Evaluates the use of technologies in an inland terminal (Magli Intermodal Service terminal), simulating current and future configurations to optimize operational flows and assess the adaptability of automation to evolving demands.

UC4. Automated Multimodal Terminal Operations: Leverages digital models to simulate automated yard layouts at the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH, analysing traffic scenarios and performance metrics to identify the most effective automation strategies.

In all use cases, simulations will compare manual and automated scenarios, identifying significant improvements in efficiency, environmental impact, and logistics synchronization.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

The European transport sector is a critical economic driver, contributing approximately 5% to the EU's GDP and employing over 10 million people. (Cartier, 2024) Freight transport is essential for regional growth and competitiveness. Freight transportation plays a crucial role in supply chain management by facilitating the efficient movement and timely delivery of raw materials and finished products. (Crainic et al., 2009)

The geographic separation between producers and consumers drives the demand for freight transportation. As trade has become increasingly globalized, traditional road transport has become less practical, necessitating the exploration of alternative modes of transportation and their combinations.

Soaring freight demand coupled with existing capacity constraints has intensified the negative externalities associated with transportation, including pollution, climate change, noise, congestion, and accidents. These issues have detrimental impacts on the economy, public health, and overall quality of life. (International Transport Forum, 2021) In this context, the importance of efficient and effective transportation cannot be overstated, as transportation costs constitute a substantial portion of the overall supply chain expenses.

Automation offers a promising solution to these challenges. Terminals and hubs, characterized by controlled environments, are ideal for implementing advanced automation technologies and improving efficiency and capacity. Nevertheless, the development of automation is fragmented across different transport modes, hindering interoperability and the realization of end-to-end automated logistics.

A lack of unified operational models and data sharing prevents the seamless movement of goods from origin to destination. To fully harness the potential of automation, a more coordinated approach is necessary to bridge the gaps between different transport modes and create a truly integrated freight system.

AutoMoTIF in a nutshell:

AutoMoTIF, with a duration of three years, will focus on the development of strategies, business and governance models, regulatory recommendations and synergies that will enable the **integration and interoperability of automated transport systems** and solutions towards the **operational automation of multimodal cargo flows and logistics supply chains** in the intra-European network.

AutoMoTIF will assess operational automation opportunities both in terms of transport infrastructure and modes, as well as multimodal logistics services and processes.

2.2 Objectives of the deliverable

Deliverable D1.1 ‘Playground and vision’ includes the State-of-the-Art analysis, technological gaps and user needs, AutoMoTIF Concept of Operations, reference architecture and scenarios per use case.

The objectives of this deliverable, are:

- Analyse and map the status of automated freight transport logistics operations, both in terms of transport infrastructure and modes, as well as multimodal logistics services and processes.
- Identify user needs and technological gaps in automated transport technologies and logistics operations between modes and hubs.
- Assess benefits of autonomous vehicles, rolling stock and vessels to multimodal logistics and the role/benefits of seamless multimodal automatic cargo transport across transport modes.
- Describe the use cases and scenarios that will bridge the technological gaps identified.
- Define the Concept of Operations providing the operations that will be performed in each use case

Provide the reference architecture to be tailored and implemented in each use case.

2.3 Methodology

For the **State-of-the-art (SotA) analysis**, a thorough literature review has been performed by all partners, including an in-depth research of research studies, sector industry reports and case studies of technology provider companies and port terminal operators. In doing so, the SotA is based on each of the four freight transport pillars and their corresponding use cases. (See Annex I)

In the rapidly evolving landscape of port logistics, understanding user needs is essential for optimizing operations. Stakeholders have specific requirements that must be met to enhance the efficiency, safety, and reliability of operational processes. By gaining insight into these user needs, organizations can tailor solutions that not only improve operational performance but also align with the strategic objectives of the industry. Equally important is the identification of technological gaps that exist within current solutions. Despite advancements in automation, there are still significant challenges that hinder the full realization of efficient and safe operations. These gaps may include limitations in automation, interoperability issues between existing and new systems, and insufficient data integration capabilities.

User needs and technological gaps have been identified by the pilot site representatives collecting feedback about current processes and needs, current technologies and barriers that hinder the implementation of operational automation of multimodal freight transport. At least, two partners involved in each use case were interviewed. In total, up to 13 AutoMoTIF partners were interviewed, as well as 2 external partners (see Annex II).

Based on the analysis, two main categories have been identified for each use case. Firstly, operational needs: these include the limitations and challenges related to the daily processes and activities of the terminals. These needs focus on efficiency, productivity, technological compatibility, and the capacity to implement automated solutions in everyday operations. Secondly, management needs: these refer to the requirements and constraints associated with strategic and managerial decision-making. In this context, the gaps are linked to existing limitations or barriers that hinder or restrict the automation process of the terminals. These limitations may stem from technical, organizational, financial, or strategic factors, depending on the specific case analysed (Annex III).

AutoMoTIF ConOps have been defined providing the operations that will be performed in each use case, the solutions that will be developed to support integration and interoperability of modes and hubs towards operational automation, as well as the high-level **reference architecture** to be implemented. The **scenarios** have been selected to refine the user needs identified in Task 1.1 and will also provide input to the development of the requirements and specifications for the AUTOMOTIF use cases (Task 1.2).

3 Introduction to multimodal freight transport automation

3.1 Multimodal freight transport

In 2022, based on tonne-km, maritime transport accounted for the 67.8 % of freight transport performance in the EU, followed by road transport with 24,9%. Rail transport represented 5.5 %, inland waterway 1.6 % and air 0.2 % (Eurostat, 2022). Freight transport continues to grow, and road freight transport is projected to increase by around 40% by 2030 and by little over 80% by 2050 (European Commission, 2023). The negative consequences of transport such as pollution, climate change, noise, congestion and accidents pose problems to the economy, health and well-being. The EU transport policy aims therefore at reducing road transport towards less polluting and more energy efficient modes of transport.

The ‘Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy’ plan (European Commission, 2020) aims to a more sustainable, green, smart and resilient mobility. It outlines how the EU's various transportation methods (like trains, cars, and airplanes) can work together to achieve these goals. Ultimately, the goal is to cut emissions by 90% by 2050. This will be achieved by making the transportation system smarter, more competitive, safer, easier to access, while still affordable.

Multimodal freight transport (MFT) refers to using at least two different modes of transport (among road, rail, sea, and air) in a journey to move goods from one point to another with the particularity of moving of goods across global supply chains under a single contract. By optimizing routes and minimizing handling, it provides a comprehensive and cost-effective approach to international trade. Goods can be transported in various transportation units (crates, pallets, cages, containers) or as loose packages loaded directly on transportation means, such as vehicles, vessels, aircrafts (Archetti et al., 2022). Multimodal transport between land and sea, such as road-rail intermodal transportation, water-rail intermodal transport and road-railway-water multimodal transport are the most frequently used combinations of modes.

MFT can take different definitions depending on the modes of transportation involved. A more specific, often used, definition is *intermodality*. Intermodal freight transportation involves the coordinated utilization of multiple modes of transport to facilitate the efficient movement of goods while maintaining the integrity of the load unit. This streamlined process eliminates the need for repeated handling and reduces the overall transportation time (Freightos, 2023).

The European freight transport industry has updated its definition of 'combined transport.' For a transport to be considered combined, more than half of the distance must be travelled by non-road modes like trains or ships. (UIRR, 2024) The goal is to increase this percentage to 60% by 2035, as more train stations and better rail infrastructure are expected to be built (Freightos, 2023).

Different terminologies related to MFT have been defined (SteadieSeifi, 2014), however, there are a few differences among these terminologies:

Terminology	Definition
Multimodal transportation (MFT)	Defined as using at least two different transport modes.
Intermodal transportation	Refers to MFT that utilizes the same loading unit.
Co-modal transportation	Increases the utilization of different modes.
Synchromodal transportation	Emphasizes the real-time operations of MFT transport

Table 1: Terminology and definition of multimodal freight transport

Multimodal transportation is divided into three phases (Archetti et al., 2022):

- **Pre-haul:** transportation from the starting location to an interchange terminal where the shipment switches modality.
- **Long-haul:** is the backbone of global trade, specializing in the movement of goods over vast distances. These journeys typically involve rail, maritime (ocean freight), inland waterways (e.g., canals and rivers), and air transportation.
- **End-haul:** also known as the last mile delivery. It is carried out by road transportation in most cases.

The following fundamental elements must be considered for the successful implementation of multimodal freight transport:

Multimodal terminals: These are indispensable facilities for the efficient transshipment of freight between various modes of transportation.

Multimodal transport network: This integrated network seamlessly connects different transportation modes, optimizing the flow of freight between shippers and receivers.

Multimodal policies: policies can encourage the integration and coordination of different transport modes. Especially on standardization and data sharing, public-private partnerships and regulatory incentives.

Effective service management: The efficient coordination of services among freight forwarders, logistics service providers, and carriers is crucial for multimodal success.

Delivery characteristics: Factors such as freight weight, dimensions, location, and customer requirements significantly influence multimodal operations.

Interoperability: interoperability between countries transportation networks is essential for establishing multimodality on a global scale.

3.2 Multimodal freight transport automation

In recent decades, automation has revolutionized numerous industries, and multimodal transportation is no exception. The growing demand for faster, more efficient, and accurate deliveries has driven the adoption of advanced technologies at all stages of the supply chain.

Automation in multimodal transportation refers to the application of technologies to optimize logistics processes. This includes everything from warehouse management and package sorting to route planning and autonomous vehicle driving. While automating cargo handling equipment are important steps for non-automated terminals, enhancing efficiency and safety requires a more comprehensive approach. Simplifying tasks and automating non-essential processes can significantly improve operations. These improvements collectively contribute to increased efficiency and safety within the terminal's operations.

Although Deliverable D3.1 provides an in-depth analysis of the economic, sociocultural, and environmental implications of automation in multimodal freight transport, these are the primary benefits and challenges identified by research studies and partners’ opinion:

3.2.1 Benefits of automation in multimodal transport

Optimisation of Operations
Time and cost savings. According to McKinsey’s study in 2018, The Future of Automated Ports, the benefits of port automation are numerous, with potential productivity increases of up to 35% and operating expenses expected to decrease by 20-55%. However, AutoMoTIF partners also highlight that financial benefits of automation are often realized over the long term, as the initial investment is substantial, and the return on investment (ROI) is not always immediately positive.
Port and shipping services are optimized through automation, which streamlines processes and minimizes the time and resources required for terminal operations. This leads to enhanced operational efficiency, shorter waiting times, and increased terminal capacity, enabling faster and more efficient cargo handling.
Efficient resource management: Automation enhances planning and resource allocation, optimizing asset and equipment use while improving forward-looking prediction capabilities.
Operability
Improved decision making: Data collected through automation allows companies to make more informed and strategic decisions, based on real-time data.
Real data can be used with advanced technologies like machine learning and deep learning to improve port operations. (Evmides et al., 2024).
Scalability: Automated solutions can easily adapt to changes in cargo demand, allowing terminals to adjust their operations more flexibly.
Improved multimodal coordination: Automation can facilitate synchronization between rail, port and truck operations and other transport modes, improving the overall efficiency of the supply chain.
Safety
Less human accidents: Automation reduces the risk of accidents by minimizing worker exposure to hazardous situations.
Enhanced control and supervision of access to restricted areas within the terminal. Automated alarm systems detect any irregularities, such as unauthorized container openings, helping to safeguard goods from theft or sabotage.
Predictive maintenance of infrastructure to detect and prevent mechanical failures.
Accuracy
Automated technologies can improve precision in cargo movements, resulting in fewer human errors and less cargo damage.
Increased accuracy in data capture and collection through tools such as AIS, RFID, and OCR, improving cargo traceability.
Positive Social and Environmental Impact
Reduce emissions in the logistics chain.
Measure and monitor emissions to raise awareness of the actual emissions generated at the terminal.

Table 2: Benefits of Automation

3.2.2 Challenges and barriers of automation in multimodal transport

Impact on the workforce
Workforce resistance: Labor unions often express their reaction to digitalization and automation under the fear of reducing the need for a human workforce
Implications for the workforce: The shift toward automation may necessitate restructuring the workforce, potentially leading to labour conflicts and retraining needs
Cultural change: Automation may require significant changes in workplace culture, which can be difficult to implement.
High initial investment
Advanced equipment: The need to incorporate advanced equipment for automation represents a significant barrier, as its high initial cost makes it difficult for many companies to invest. Additionally, during the transition process, the equipment can cause delays and significant production losses for terminals.
Digital infrastructure: the need for a robust digital infrastructure, including reliable networks, cloud storage, and cybersecurity measures, adds significant upfront costs for companies transitioning to automation, which can discourage investment.
Lack of funding: many businesses struggle to secure sufficient capital to cover the high initial costs associated with implementing advanced automation technologies, plus in the short term, they don't see a return on investment. However, some funding aids are being made available to address this barrier, such as the PORTS 4.0 grants in Spain, as stated by the BilbaoLab Port.
Critical infrastructure
Lack of long-term strategy by terminals. Many port companies tend to focus on immediate challenges and short-term goals, rather than developing a clear long-term strategy for their operations. This often makes it difficult for them to plan for future growth or keep up with changing industry trends. To stay competitive and ensure sustainable growth, it's essential for these companies to adopt a more forward-thinking approach.
Integration with existing systems: Compatibility between new automated technologies and legacy systems can be complicated and may require substantial adjustments.
Dependence on technology: High reliance on automated systems can raise concerns about vulnerability to technical failures.
Data management and security: Collecting and analysing real-time data raises concerns about privacy and data security, considering that terminals are highly vulnerable to potential cyberattacks.
Interoperability Issues
Inconsistent standardization for data integration: Inadequate data standardization can hinder effective communication and coordination between different automated processes, and real-time tracking systems must be able to handle this data.
Variety and diversity of cargo: need of specialized equipment for non-container cargo. Automation systems must be versatile enough to accommodate these different handling requirements, which can complicate the design and implementation of automated solutions.
Multiple stakeholders with different interests: Establish comprehensive procedures for the implementation and operation of automated systems and involving all relevant stakeholders in the planning and implementation process, providing clear information and training to effectively monitor and intervene when necessary.

Supply chain impact: Changes in operations may affect partners and suppliers within the supply chain, requiring careful management of business relationships.
Lack of digital skills and a qualified labour force
Maintenance and support: The need for skilled personnel to maintain and manage automated systems can create an additional burden.
Skills development: Training these existing personnel to work with new automated technologies can be a costly and time-consuming process.
Legal and regulatory framework
Determining liability in case of accidents or incidents involving automated systems can be complex and may require new legal frameworks.
Navigating the regulatory framework governing transport operations can pose challenges when implementing automation.

Table 3: Challenges and barriers of Automation

4 Emerging technologies

The logistics and transportation sectors are undergoing a significant transformation driven by the rapid advancement of emerging technologies. As global supply chains become increasingly complex and consumer demands for faster and more reliable services grow, the integration of innovative technologies has become essential to enhance operational efficiency and maintain competitiveness.

As stakeholders in the logistics industry continue to seek solutions to meet the demands of modern transportation, understanding and leveraging these emerging technologies is critical.

This section will explore the various technologies shaping the future of multimodal transport, detailing their applications and the potential benefits they offer to enhance operations within terminals and across supply chains.

Below is a list of the most relevant emerging technologies in the sector, along with a brief description and their application.

Digital Twins, due to their importance and implementation in the AutoMoTIF project, and Artificial Intelligence, due to its emergence and current potential in the automation of multimodal transport, are discussed in greater detail in sections 4.1 and 4.2.

Emerging technologies	
Internet of Things (IoT)	<p><u>Description:</u> IoT, as defined by Zhang et al. (2017), refers to 'networks of connected ships and shore-based facilities equipped with digital entities.' In the shipping sector, IoT operates across five key functions: sensing, heterogeneous networking, data computation, services and applications, and exhibition. Implementing IoT technology in the maritime and rail industry is crucial for providing stakeholders with access to valuable data and information, enhancing decision-making and operational efficiency. (Bouhal, 2022).</p>

	<p><u>Application:</u> A network of smart sensors and actuators, wireless devices, and data centers make up the key infrastructure of the smart port, which allows the port authorities to provide essential services in a faster and more efficient manner.</p> <p>In recent years, the global sensor market has expanded year by year, and it is expected to maintain high growth rates in the future. (Yang et al. 2018). IoT is also expected to be a key enabler in rail freight transport for the deployment of the Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC), the Intelligent Video Gates (IVG) or smart containers. (Djordjevic, 2024)</p>
<p>Big Data Analytics</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Big Data Analytics involves processing and analyzing large and complex data sets to extract meaningful insights. Big data analytics implemented in smart ports can gain real-time visibility into the movement of cargo, enabling better planning and resource allocation, and is needed to machine learning algorithms. By predictive analytics port authorities and terminal companies can proactively identify and address issues before they escalate, identify peak periods of activity and anticipate. (Cserhat, 2023)</p> <p><u>Application:</u> Big data is implemented to develop a predictive analytics solution, detect anomalies in cargo and security. Port of Rotterdam implemented Big Data to predict vessel arrival times according to factors such as congestion, tides and weather conditions. (Cserhat, 2023)</p>
<p>Blockchain Technology</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Although Blockchain technology is known to cryptocurrency uses, this technology can be used to make data immutable (not altered). Since a block cannot be changed, the only trust needed is at entering data by agents. A blockchain allows the data in a database to be spread out among several network nodes at various locations. Multimodal freight transport is characterized by one-bill contract mode. Blockchain technology can effectively address issues such as a lack of trust and difficulties in information sharing in this type of contract. However, in a blockchain-based multimodal transport platform, participants will have to collaborate and share information such as consignment demands and transport resources. (Qian et al., 2024)</p> <p><u>Application:</u> In multimodal transport, Blockchain enhances transparency and traceability in supply chains by allowing all parties to access a secure record of cargo movements and transactions. This technology reduces the risk of fraud, ensures compliance with regulations, and enhances accountability across the logistics chain. In the railway freight sector, blockchain provide improvements into three main groups: cross-border operations, logistics chain and data distribution. (Tardivo et al., 2023)</p>
<p>5G Networks</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> To support smart ports and technologies (such as autonomous vehicles, container monitoring, predictive maintenance, etc.), 5G networks are key by offering ultra-fast data transmission speeds, low latency, and the ability to connect a vast number of devices simultaneously. This connectivity enables seamless communication across the terminal. (CM, 2022)</p>

	<p><u>Application:</u> In multimodal transport, 5G networks facilitate real-time tracking and communication between vehicles, terminals, and management systems. Ports like Tyne, Barcelona or the East-West Gate Terminal in Hungary have implemented a 5G radio infrastructure to develop a private 5G network to advance connectivity, mobility and safety. (Blackman, 2024)</p>
<p>Automated Robot Cranes (ARC)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> ARC are cranes integrated with AI to optimize the performance of these tasks. ARC also are equipped with object detection technologies to identify workers or objects in order to avoid collisions and accidents during operations. (Hub, 2020)</p> <p><u>Application:</u> ARC is growing in the freight and logistics industry. Port of Shanghai, Brisbane or Victorian implemented this technology (However, transition to this technology suppose multiple changes in the existing infrastructure of the terminal, from control centre to maintenance facilities and communication systems) (Hub, 2020)</p>
<p>Automated Vehicles</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Autonomous Vehicles are formed with sensors, cameras, and AI technologies that makes them able to navigate and operate without any or almost any human intervention. In the context of this project, this type of technologies is designed to transport cargo efficiently across various transport modes.</p> <p><u>Application:</u> In multimodal terminals, autonomous vehicles are used the final stages of the process or delivery, as well as for transporting different types of cargo within the terminal. By eliminating the need for human drivers, these vehicles can reduce both, labour costs and improve operational speed.</p>
<p>Smart Warehousing Solutions</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Smart Warehousing Solutions is formed by a combination of robotics, AI, and IoT and the objective of this type of technologies is to automate and optimize warehouse operations. These technologies facilitate efficient inventory management and all the orders achievement.</p> <p><u>Application:</u> In logistics terms, smart warehouses employ automated systems for sorting, storing, and retrieving cargo, significantly reducing manual labour and increasing the performance of each of these operations.</p>
<p>Advanced Traffic Management Systems</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Advanced Traffic Management Systems use real-time data and predictive analytics (as explained below, Machine Learning contributes to predictive analysis) to monitor and manage traffic flows in the context of multimodal terminal operations. They able the managers to predict the routes and the schedules in the terminal operations.</p> <p><u>Application:</u> In multimodal terminals, these systems optimize the movement of vehicles and cargo and reduce the congestion and improve the efficiency of all the operations.</p>

Table 4: Emerging Technologies

4.1 Digital Twin

The concept of a Digital Twin (DT) refers to a virtual replica of a physical asset, system, or process that captures data from sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices to reflect the state, history, and behaviour of its physical counterpart.

While DT can receive and update with real-time data, this is not a fundamental requirement in all cases; instead, their key characteristic is the ability to collect, store, and manage data to support simulations, predictive analysis, and prescriptive modelling. This flexible approach enables Digital Twins to operate with both real-time and buffered or historical data, depending on the specific application requirements.

The development of Digital Twins in logistical environments, such as ports and intermodal terminals, has advanced significantly in recent years. Initially conceived as basic digital models for visualization and planning, DT have now evolved into sophisticated systems capable of monitoring, simulating, and optimizing operations in real-time. This evolution is driven by advancements in technologies like IoT, artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and cloud computing, enabling greater precision, efficiency, and responsiveness in logistical operations.

The evolution of Digital Twins can be classified into four stages of technological maturity, each representing an increase in system interoperability, scalability, and autonomy:

1. **Basic Digital Representation**
2. **Enhanced Digital Representation (Digital Shadow)**
3. **Connected Digital Twin**
4. **Autonomous Digital Twin**

The four levels of Digital Twin and its relationship with the proposed open reference architecture for Digital Twins will be further developed in chapter 5.

This efficiency gained with the use of the DT technologies, is primarily due to the ability to simulate various operational scenarios, allowing stakeholders to identify bottlenecks and optimize resource allocation without disrupting actual operations. Additionally, Digital Twins support predictive maintenance, which leverages historical and real-time data to forecast equipment failures before they occur. This capability not only extends the lifespan of physical assets but also leads to substantial cost savings in maintenance and repairs.

The development of Digital Twin technology represents a transformative shift in logistics and operational management. By evolving from static digital representations to fully autonomous systems, Digital Twins offers an impressive potential to the market and environment. As logistical hubs, such as ports and intermodal terminals, increasingly adopt Digital Twins, they are equipped to meet the challenges of modern supply chains, achieving greater precision, sustainability, and operational continuity in a rapidly evolving industry.

As an interesting example, Cosco Shipping Ports (Valencia Terminal, in Spain) developed a DT of the terminal in collaboration with Data and System Planning (DSP) and TALUMIS. This technology supports container terminals in making informed decisions by enhancing operational efficiency, managing large volumes of data, and mitigating risks, evaluating the impact of sudden shocks and disruptions This

technology provides more efficient decision-making processes, ultimately improving the overall performance of the terminal. (Container News, 2021)

4.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Today, ports and terminals face greater challenges in improving efficiency, reducing environmental impact and remaining competitive. In this context, artificial intelligence (AI) is proving to be a groundbreaking solution. Their potential to transform multimodal transport is huge, providing an opportunity to streamline logistics and improve safety across different modes of transport.

AI is already having an impact in areas such as automating systems, optimizing routes, predicting estimated times of arrival (ETA), scheduling ships, managing cargo, improving traffic flows and enabling predictive maintenance. (Harder, 2024). The key role of AI is to process data to enhance long-term decision-making (Savelsberg, n.d.). It is also expected that IA can play a central role to protect IoT devices from cybersecurity threats (Djordjevic, 2024).

In cargo handling process, the integration of AI has the potential to tackle the challenges of achieving partial or full automation. In cargo handling, it is important to automatize decision-making in critical areas such as loading order selection, hoisting preparation, and crane attachment. Automated decision-making will enhance both safety and operational efficiency (Merz et al. 2023).

According to Restack (n.d.), to effectively implement multimodal transport solutions, the following key strategies must be considered:

- **Connecting systems:** Use AI to bring together data from various transportation modes, enabling seamless coordination and real-time decision-making for more efficient route planning.
- **Prediction and optimization:** Leverage AI to analyze data to predict future needs and optimize transport schedules to reduce delays.
- **Agents experience:** Develop user-centric platforms that deliver real-time information about transport choices, schedule adjustments, and potential disruptions, enhancing the travel experience with greater convenience and efficiency.

Machine learning (ML) is considered a subset of AI and can be implemented as a data-driven decision-making tool. ML algorithms can predict travel times in multimodal transport; however, limited research has been conducted on freight transport applications. There is potential for further exploration in areas such as demand prediction, landside and seaside operations, and safety (Mekkaoui et al., 2022).

In the shipping industry, ML is utilized to enhance routing and scheduling, forecast demand fluctuations, optimize warehouse management, and support operations research. The growing demand for more efficient, data-driven port operations is expected to increasingly replace and complement traditional methods (Filom et al., 2022). ML also has applications in key logistics technologies, such as image recognition for container damage assessment and autonomous driving (Djordjevic, 2024).

AI is considered as an emerging technology, although it still has the capacity to reshape the future of port industry and there are already some examples in a real-world application of AI. In Port of Rotterdam, AI is used to optimize operations, monitor vessel traffic, improve crane efficiency, predict maintenance and reduce energy consumption (Port of Rotterdam, n.d.). The Duisburg Gateway Terminal (DGT) is leveraging

AI technologies to streamline intermodal logistics. AI will be implemented to enhance barge handling, crane optimization, train loading operations, container stacking, and to facilitate the billing and booking process within the TOS platform. (Arendasova, 2024)

As previously mentioned in the section on benefits and challenges, the key barriers to adopting AI in transport operations include the difficulty of securing financing and investment in the technology, ensuring the security of data, and integrating AI-driven processes with terminal staff operations.

Terminals and ports that incorporate AI technologies will be better equipped to foresee and resolve issues proactively. Nevertheless, the successful implementation of this transformation depends significantly on collaboration among all stakeholders. Shippers, carriers, and logistics service providers must utilize collaborative digital platforms to facilitate the sharing of data, which is essential for training AI models. (Harder, 2024)

5 Reference Architecture for Digital Twins

At first, Digital Twins were closed, monolithic systems that functioned as immobile copies of real-world assets. They had limited integration options and real-time capabilities. With the development of data analytics and the Internet of Things, these systems evolved into more open architectures that allowed for real-time data interchange and insights. Because of its modular components, this innovation produced hybrid systems that provided more flexibility and adaptability.

Today, we are moving closer to the era of open, modular, and interoperable digital twins due to the need for seamless integration, scalability, and advanced functionality. Because of this shift, architectures must be dependable, flexible, and able to incorporate multiple external systems while retaining a solid base of core functionalities. Advanced features like autonomous operation, predictive analytics, and real-time optimization are made possible by these kinds of systems. (Heilig, 2023)

5.1 Digital Twins Levels

As mentioned, the concept of Digital Twins (DT) in ports has undergone significant evolution, reflecting the growing complexity of technological integration and operational efficiency. Digital Twins, which began as simple digital representations of physical port assets, have evolved into sophisticated systems that simulate, monitor, and optimize port operations in real time.

As introduced in Section 4.1, Digital Twins can be classified into four different stages/levels. Each stage represents a progressive enhancement in technological capability, data integration, and functional utility. This evolution mirrors the advancements in IoT, AI, big data, and real-time analytics, making ports more intelligent, responsive, and efficient. In this section, we outline the key stages of Digital Twin maturity in ports, from basic digital models to fully integrated and autonomous systems, supported by real-world examples.

Level 1: Basic Digital Representation

- **Description:** In its earliest form, a Digital Twin in the port context is essentially a static digital model, a digital replica of physical assets such as cranes, containers, or transport infrastructure. These

models are often visual, or CAD representations used primarily for design, planning, and basic simulations.

- **Technologies Involved:**
 - o Basic KPI visualization and measuring tools
 - o Basic CAD software
 - o Minimal IoT integration
- **Implications:** At this stage, the Digital Twin is mostly passive and offers limited operational insight. It is primarily used for visualization and planning rather than real-time operational control. The model does not have real-time feedback loops from the physical assets it represents, limiting its usefulness in dynamic environments such as ports.

Level 2: Enhanced Digital Representation

- **Description:** In the second stage of maturity, the Digital Twin evolves into a “Digital Shadow”, where real-time data from physical assets are captured and fed into the digital model. However, the flow of information is unidirectional — from the physical asset to the digital representation, without influencing the physical system.
- **Technologies Involved:**
 - o IoT sensors for real-time data collection (e.g., sensors on cranes or trucks)
 - o Data storage and visualization platforms
 - o Limited analytics capabilities
- **Implications:** Ports in this stage begin to see improved operational insights by monitoring key parameters such as container movement, equipment usage, and infrastructure condition. However, while the digital model can provide real-time status updates, it does not yet optimize or control physical operations directly.

Level 3: Connected Digital Twin

- **Description:** This stage represents a fully connected Digital Twin with bidirectional data exchange between the digital model and the physical environment. Real-time data from port assets, such as cargo containers, vehicles, and cranes, are not only monitored but also used to optimize operations dynamically. The Digital Twin can simulate future scenarios and suggest actions to improve efficiency.
- **Technologies Involved:**
 - o IoT networks with bi-directional communication
 - o Real-time analytics and optimization algorithms
 - o AI-driven decision support systems
 - o Cloud platforms for data processing and storage
- **Implications:** At this stage, the Digital Twin begins to transform port operations. By integrating predictive analytics and decision-making capabilities, it enables ports to optimize asset usage, reduce downtime, and enhance supply chain management. Ports can also simulate different operational scenarios to test responses to potential disruptions.

Level 4: Autonomous Digital Twin:

- **Description:** The highest level of Digital Twin maturity in ports is the Autonomous Digital Twin, which not only predicts and optimizes but also autonomously controls certain aspects of port operations. This stage represents the pinnacle of automation, where the Digital Twin can self-regulate and adapt to changes without human intervention.
- **Technologies Involved:**
 - o Autonomous systems (e.g., automated cranes and vehicles)
 - o Advanced AI and machine learning for decision-making
 - o Real-time data integration from multiple systems (port logistics, vessel tracking, weather data)
 - o Edge computing for localized decision-making
- **Implications:** Ports at this stage experience maximum efficiency gains. The Digital Twin acts as an autonomous operational layer, making decisions such as rerouting vehicles, adjusting crane operations, and reassigning docking spaces based on real-time conditions. Human operators are only involved in overseeing critical or exceptional situations. This level of automation significantly reduces operational costs, minimizes human error, and enhances safety.

5.2 Open Reference Architecture for Smart Digital Twin

The rapid evolution of Digital Twin technology has brought significant advancements, but it has also introduced new challenges that must be addressed in today's era of open and modular systems. As Digital Twins transition from monolithic, closed architectures to scalable, interoperable solutions, the complexity of managing diverse data sources, integrating legacy systems, and enabling advanced functionalities has grown exponentially (Sánchez-Ayra, 2024).

In the current era, characterized by the demand for **interoperability, modularity, and scalability**, organizations face critical challenges when building and managing Digital Twins (Port of Barcelona, n.d.).

These challenges include:

- **Integration of diverse systems:** Digital Twins often rely on data from multiple sources, including IoT devices, legacy systems, external APIs, and cloud platforms. Ensuring seamless integration across these diverse systems requires robust communication protocols and interoperability standards.
- **Scalability to meet expanding needs:** As organizations grow, their Digital Twin solutions must scale to accommodate increased data volumes, more complex simulations, and additional AI-driven functionalities without compromising performance.
- **Customization for domain-specific requirements:** Different industries and use cases demand tailored Digital Twin implementations. A rigid architecture limits adaptability and restricts the adoption of advanced capabilities like predictive analytics and autonomous decision-making.
- **Ensuring security and data governance:** The integration of real-time data from various sources introduces vulnerabilities that must be mitigated through strong security measures, access controls, and compliance with data governance standards.

To address these challenges, the **Open Digital Twin Reference Architecture** is developed in the context of AUTOMOTIF project. This work will be introduced in the context of the Use Cases (see Chapter 6) as a

reference architecture to support their implementation in real environments. The framework provides a **structured and modular approach** to designing Digital Twins that meet the demands of interoperability and scalability while also offering a foundation for future advancements. By focusing on three key layers—**external integration, core functionality, and intermediary integration mechanisms**—this architecture ensures a seamless flow of data and operations between external systems and the Digital Twin’s internal components (McKee, 2023).

The Open Reference Architecture is specifically designed to overcome the limitations of traditional **closed systems**, which are often rigid, monolithic, and difficult to expand. In a closed architecture, components are tightly coupled and proprietary, meaning that integrations with external systems, modules, or technologies are either not possible or require significant customization. These architectures are typically confined to a specific vendor or platform, limiting flexibility, adaptability, and scalability.

In contrast, an **open architecture** provides a framework that is **modular, interoperable, and expandable**. It is “open” in the sense that it enables the seamless integration of external components, tools, and technologies from various providers, making it highly adaptable to the evolving needs of organizations. This openness does not imply that the system is “free” or unregulated; instead, it refers to the system’s **ability to interoperate with diverse external modules** while maintaining a standardized core. (Klar, 2023)

In that way, it is possible to summarize the core attributes of an open architecture for Digital Twins as following:

- **Modularity:** The architecture is designed so that individual components, such as AI models, simulation engines, or data processing tools, can be independently added, removed, or replaced without disrupting the system’s core functionality. This ensures organizations can tailor the architecture to their specific use cases and scale as needed.
- **Interoperability:** Open architectures rely on standardized protocols, APIs, and communication frameworks to enable seamless integration with third-party systems and tools. This includes legacy systems, IoT devices, cloud platforms, and external simulation engines, facilitating data exchange and collaboration across diverse technologies.
- **Scalability:** An open architecture allows the system to grow in both complexity and capacity. Organizations can incorporate additional sensors, data sources, and processing capabilities as operational demands increase without requiring a complete system overhaul.
- **Vendor Independence:** Unlike closed systems, which often lock organizations into a single vendor’s ecosystem, open architectures enable the integration of tools and components from multiple providers. This flexibility ensures that organizations can leverage the best available technologies and adapt to emerging advancements.
- **Future-Proofing:** Open architectures are designed to evolve with technological advancements. As new standards, tools, and methodologies emerge, these architectures can incorporate innovations without requiring significant structural changes.

By leveraging the principles of openness, the Digital Twin Reference Architecture ensures that organizations can:

- **Integrate and interact seamlessly** with external systems, such as AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems.
- **Provide a flexible and modular foundation** for implementing domain-specific use cases while maintaining compatibility with emerging technologies.
- **Facilitate scalability** by allowing the addition of new data sources, functionalities, and capabilities without disrupting existing operations.
- **Support advanced functionalities** such as real-time optimization, predictive analytics, and autonomous decision-making, enabling Digital Twins to reach the highest levels of maturity.

Following those principles, the Open Reference Architecture for Smart Digital Twins has been designed as shown in the following diagram. There, each layer addresses the challenges of being modular, interoperable, scalable, and future-ready. This ensures organizations can build robust, adaptable solutions that remain relevant in an ever-evolving technological landscape.

Figure 1: Diagram of the Open Reference Architecture for Smart Digital Twin (elaborated by Mosaic)

The Digital Twin Reference Architecture presented here provides a modular, interoperable, and scalable framework. It is structured into three primary layers, each with distinct roles and functionalities:

1. Outer Layer: Integration and Interoperability with External Systems

This layer is focused on connecting the Digital Twin to external systems and data sources. It defines the interfaces and mechanisms required to achieve seamless integration and data exchange with these external entities. The five main external components highlighted in this layer are:

- **AI models:** Advanced AI models for prediction, optimization, and decision-making. These models may include machine learning algorithms, reinforcement learning, or domain-specific AI systems.
- **Simulation engines:** Tools for running dynamic simulations, enabling the Digital Twin to test various scenarios and predict system behaviors.
- **Data sources:** IoT devices, legacy systems, external databases, and real-time feeds providing the foundational data for Digital Twin operations.
- **Client applications:** User-facing tools for visualization, monitoring, and interaction with the Digital Twin, such as dashboards, mobile apps, or control systems.
- **Legacy systems:** Existing infrastructure and systems that need to be integrated without disrupting current workflows.

This layer emphasizes interoperability through APIs, communication protocols, and standardized data formats to ensure that the Digital Twin can operate in a diverse ecosystem.

2. Middle Layer: Core integration and communication functionalities

The middle layer acts as the **integration and communication bridge** between the external layer and the internal core. It houses the fundamental services and tools necessary for data processing, transformation, and communication. Key components include:

- **API Gateway and communication layer:** Facilitates seamless and secure communication between external systems and the Digital Twin. This component ensures compatibility with various data formats and protocols.
- **Data processing and transformation:** Responsible for cleaning, organizing, and converting raw data into a format suitable for core Digital Twin functionalities.
- **Workflow orchestration:** Manages the flow of data and tasks across the system, ensuring that different modules work together efficiently.
- **Event handling and notification:** Tracks changes in the environment or system states, triggering appropriate responses or notifying relevant stakeholders.
- **Security and access control:** Ensures that all data exchanges and operations are secure, with role-based access controls and encryption mechanisms.

This layer is essential for enabling interoperability, as it standardizes the flow of information and operations between the external systems and the internal components.

3. Inner layer: Core functionalities of the Digital Twin

At the heart of the architecture lies the **core functionality layer**, which encompasses the essential components that define the capabilities of any Digital Twin. These core components are:

- **Information model:** Represents the structure and semantics of the data within the Digital Twin. It acts as a blueprint for understanding and processing information.

- **Data storage layer:** Stores and organizes data for historical analysis, real-time processing, and future predictions.
- **AI/ML Model Manager:** Oversees the deployment, monitoring, and optimization of AI and machine learning models used within the Digital Twin.
- **Simulation and analysis controller:** Directs the execution of simulations, enabling the Digital Twin to analyze scenarios and make predictions.
- **Business rules engine:** Governs the decision-making processes based on predefined rules and conditions, ensuring alignment with business objectives.

This layer provides the foundational capabilities that enable a Digital Twin to function effectively, including simulation, optimization, prediction, and decision-making.

Key Features of the Reference Architecture

The architecture's design ensures that all three layers work cohesively to deliver a comprehensive, interoperable, and scalable Digital Twin. Its modular nature allows for the independent upgrading and replacement of components, while its interoperability ensures seamless integration with diverse systems. Additionally, its scalability supports growth and the integration of advanced functionalities as technology evolves.

By adopting this reference architecture, organizations can build Digital Twins that are not only capable of real-time monitoring and optimization but also adaptable to future advancements and operational needs. This framework is essential for advancing through the Digital Twin maturity levels, from basic digital representations to autonomous systems.

5.3 Implementation of the Open Reference Architecture to the Digital Twins Levels

The **Open Reference Architecture for Digital Twins** provides a modular and scalable framework that enables the integration and progression of Digital Twin functionalities across their maturity levels, as illustrated in the **Digital Twin Levels** (Klar, 2023) diagram below. This diagram highlights how capabilities such as data acquisition, integration, simulation, optimization, and user interaction evolve from static representations (Level 1) to fully autonomous systems (Level 4), while emphasizing the growing focus on interoperability with external systems.

This architecture serves as a critical enabler for **the four use cases described in Chapter 6**, where it guides the implementation of essential functionalities in **port automation**, logistics optimization, and real-time visualization. By supporting seamless integration with IoT devices, AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems, the architecture provides the tools needed to achieve greater levels of automation and decision-making efficiency.

Through its scalability, the Open Reference Architecture ensures that these use cases can progressively activate and expand functionalities as they move towards higher levels of Digital Twin maturity. It lays the foundation for transforming port operations, streamlining logistics networks, and enhancing supply chain visibility, aligning each use case with the maturity progression and interoperability focus outlined in the diagram below.

Figure 2: Digital Twin Levels with Open Reference Architecture (elaborated by Mosaic)

Diagram Explanation: Increasing Complexity and Interoperability Across Levels

The diagram represents the progressive maturity of Digital Twins, highlighting how the Open Reference Architecture facilitates the activation of critical capabilities at each level. Below is an explanation of the key aspects visualized in the diagram:

1. Progressive Activation of Capabilities

Each phase of Digital Twin maturity reflects a different set of functionalities and technological sophistication:

- **Level 1 (Basic Digital Representation):** At this stage, only foundational capabilities such as **user interaction** and **basic data acquisition** are activated. The focus is on static visualizations, supported by CAD tools or KPI dashboards. Integration with external systems is minimal, emphasizing the system’s internal modularity to support future upgrades.
- **Level 2 (Enhanced Digital Representation):** This phase introduces **real-time data acquisition** through IoT sensors and **limited integration** with external systems like data visualization platforms. Functionalities such as **basic simulation** begin to emerge, providing insights for monitoring and diagnostics, but predictive capabilities remain undeveloped.
- **Level 3 (Connected Digital Twin):** This level is marked by the integration of **bi-directional data exchange** and advanced **simulation engines**. **Optimization and prediction** capabilities are enabled through AI-driven insights, while **real-time visualization and interaction tools** allow users to monitor and dynamically adjust operations. The modular nature of the architecture ensures scalability and interoperability with external AI models and cloud platforms.
- **Level 4 (Autonomous Digital Twin):** At this stage, all capabilities are fully operational, with an emphasis on **autonomous decision-making** and **real-time system self-regulation**. The architecture’s inner layers, such as the **business rules engine**, fully orchestrate workflows, while edge computing ensures localized decision-making. External integration with autonomous systems like self-driving vehicles and automated cranes is seamless, leveraging the open and scalable framework.

2. Interoperability Focus Across Levels

The **interoperability focus**, as depicted in the diagram, illustrates how openness to external providers expands with each level:

- **Level 1:** Integration is limited to static tools, such as visualization dashboards, without real-time external data flows.
- **Level 2:** Partial integration enables basic monitoring through IoT sensors, with external data enhancing awareness and diagnostics.
- **Level 3:** Full integration supports bidirectional data exchange, enabling real-time optimization and operational decision-making.
- **Level 4:** Autonomous AI and orchestration systems rely on continuous interaction with external components, such as edge computing and external APIs, to achieve real-time, dynamic self-regulation.

3. Alignment with the Reference Architecture

The diagram complements the Open Reference Architecture by visually mapping the gradual activation of its layers at each level:

- The **outer layer** becomes increasingly critical as Digital Twins advance, ensuring seamless interoperability with AI models, simulation engines, and legacy systems.
- The **middle layer** facilitates bi-directional communication and workflow orchestration as more sophisticated integration and optimization capabilities are required.

- The **core layer** consistently expands its role, from managing static data and simulations in Level 1 to enabling real-time predictive and autonomous operations in Level 4.

Enabling Open, Modular, and Scalable Digital Twins

The Open Reference Architecture ensures that Digital Twins at every level can evolve incrementally while maintaining compatibility with existing systems. As seen in the diagram, the architecture's modular and scalable design enables the progressive activation of capabilities, ensuring that organizations can seamlessly transition to higher levels of maturity without disruption.

This approach empowers organizations to:

- Build flexible systems at early stages that can grow in complexity.
- Achieve full interoperability and autonomy at the highest levels.
- Leverage cutting-edge technologies to optimize operational efficiency, enhance decision-making, and maximize scalability.

6 Specific use cases for AutoMoTIF

6.1 UC1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels

6.1.1 Use Case definition

6.1.1.1 Purpose and Scope

UC1 focuses on analysing and studying the advantages of utilising automation across all phases of the port call process. This includes the vessel's arrival at the port, which encompasses the initial announcement, allocation of berth windows as well as the tugboats assignment. The process continues with the vessel's manoeuvring and docking, both performed by the assigned tugboats, followed by the stevedoring operations that secure the vessel on the quay to initiate the cargo loading and unloading processes. The undocking and manoeuvring of the vessel as it departs from the port is also included in UC1. Automated stevedore operations are investigated in UC2 and are therefore not within the scope of UC1.

The overall aim of the UC is to identify the basic requirements for a seamless and automated port call process. Additionally, the UC aims to verify the expected benefits from the implementation of automation in the process in terms of operational efficiency, safety, and environmental impact. To achieve the UC's objectives, the entire process will be simulated to replicate the complex interactions among the process key players as well as the main parameters that have a significant impact on the port call process (e.g. weather conditions, size of the vessel, number of tugboats etc.).

6.1.1.2 General Overview of the Use Case

UC1 will simulate the entire process of berthing and unberthing at a generic port (i.e. container terminal), with the assumption that the operation will be performed by fully autonomous tugboats (i.e., without a master onboard) and that an Automated Mooring System is installed at the quay. The simulation will incorporate various key parameters for the process, such as vessel size, wind speed, significant wave

height, and other environmental conditions, to create a realistic and comprehensive model. Additionally, data flows will be carefully considered to demonstrate the potential benefits of integrating automation into this specific process.

6.1.2 State-of-the-Art analysis of automated vessel calls

In the realm of the automation of freight transportation, vessel port calls hold particular significance as they represent the critical junctures where maritime vessels interface with land-based logistics networks. These calls serve as orchestrated events that facilitate the seamless movement of goods across international borders and supply chains.

Current research on vessel automation is primarily focused on enhancing vessel autonomy through the development of sophisticated navigation and control systems, addressing communication and connectivity challenges, improving situational awareness for collision avoidance and safety, and exploring commercial viability and necessary regulatory frameworks. However, there are significant gaps related to the automated operation of vessels when calling ports. Research that investigates parts of this process has been conducted in the context of EC-funded projects such as MOSES, AEGIS, AUTOSHIP and SEAMLESS focusing mainly on autonomous ship navigation, automated loading and unloading, automated manoeuvring and docking and shore control stations that deal with the exchange of data required for the technical integration rather than the business one.

Port call optimization needs to be integrated with inbound and outbound logistics. Port operations are complex as they are intended to serve sea and land transport simultaneously and consist of multiple actors who must act cooperatively for the port to be an effective hub.

The exchange of crucial information such as stowage plans, loading/discharging plans, berthing place, etc. are often ignored thus making the adoption of automated vessel operations for commercial exploitation practically impossible. As AutoMoTIF focuses on simulating the whole process of an automated vessel call for container operations, starting from the point of confirming the call and sharing data such as vessel specifics, EDI files, ETAs and loading/discharge sequences until the vessel departure from the port, we may analyse the entire process, which involves coordination between the ship, port authority, and other stakeholders.

Figure 3 shows the phases included in an ordinary port call process and Table 5 describes each phase. The phases shown in blue are considered part of the UC1, whereas the Cargo Operations phase is out of the scope of UC1.

Figure 3: Ordinary port call process

Phase	Description
<p>1. Planning for Arrival</p>	<p>This phase involves the initial preparations and communication between the vessel and the port authority.</p> <p>Berth planning for an arriving ship is usually organized by the terminal operating that berth: it tells which ship will be moored at which berthing position, which side alongside and at what time. Key activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time of arrival notification: advance notice and berth allocation of the cargo, route planning, port selection, estimated ETA. - Vessel planning: tugboat assignment based on maximum sizes and conditions, availability of the berth, fairway, nautical services and clearance. - Port clearance, regarding regulation and documentation. Essential information like cargo details, and specific needs of the ship are shared with the ship's agent, port authorities and container terminal.
<p>2. Berthing</p>	<p>Berthing is the process of safely navigating a vessel into its designated position alongside a pier, quay, or dock.</p> <p>Requires communication between the ship, port authority and terminal operators. During this pre-mooring phase, the ship needs to provide all required information. The process of berthing or docking, involves several key phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approach: vessel positioning, communication and manoeuvring with tug assistance. - Berthing: mooring lines to secure the ship to the berth, fendering to protect the ship and the berth from damage during the docking process. - Gangway Deployment: Once the ship is safely docked, the crew extends and connects a walkway between the vessel and the pier. - Securing: additional lines if needed, fine-tuning and safety checks.
<p>3. Cargo Operations</p>	<p>The loading and unloading process of a vessel represents a highly intricate operation, requiring thorough planning and seamless coordination among various stakeholders.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation: Previous starting cargo operations, planning the optimal sequence for loading and unloading is required. This step also includes getting equipment like cranes, forklifts, and conveyors ready. - Cargo handling: depending on the level of automation, using cranes or automated cranes and other machinery required to transfer cargo between the ship and the quayside. This includes stowing the cargo as well as conducting inspections. - Verification: Once the goods have been unloaded, a verification must be carried out to ensure that all the shipments have been received and are in good condition - Post-operation Tasks: Securing the cargo after handling to ensure it is safe for transport or storage.
<p>4. Unberthing and Departure</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation: cargo securing, removing equipment and safety checks.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Undocking: Mooring line release, tugboats assist the vessel in manoeuvring away from the berth. - Departure: The vessel departs the port after maintaining communication with port authorities and vessels in the area, following the designated departure route and adhering to maritime traffic regulations.
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Table 5: Call process Phases

6.1.2.1 Current technology state

The vessel calls phases, outlined above, involve a complex interplay of activities implemented by different technologies:

1. Planning for arrival:

The logistical planning for a port operation typically encompasses the scheduling of berths and quay cranes, the planning of vessel routes, and the accurate prediction of vessel arrival times. However, a significant challenge arises from the frequent deviations of ships from their anticipated arrival times, which can lead to disruptions in the plan.

Planning for arrival	
Port Management System (PMS) / Terminal Operating Systems (TOS)	<u>Description:</u> Integrated software solutions are developed to manage internal port operations efficiently. Port authorities and terminal operators have the responsibility for managing port facilities and operations. Over recent decades, these systems have undergone significant advancements, integrating cutting-edge technologies to enhance their functionality and effectiveness (Hernandez et al., 2024).
	<u>Current Applications:</u> PMS/TOS is currently integrated in large ports, which have a high volume of traffic and arrival.
Port Collaborative Decision Making (PortCDM)	<u>Description:</u> PortCDM facilitates the exchange of operational information among key stakeholders involved in port call processes. By centralizing all port call-related events in a single platform, the system provides a unified view of operations, enabling better coordination and optimized planning for all parties. (Lind et al., 2019).
	<u>Current Applications:</u> PortCDM meets the demands from shipping companies to adjust just-in-time arrivals and departures.
Port Community Systems (PCS)	<u>Description:</u> PCS are digital collaborative platforms that enable seamless exchange of information among a port's many stakeholders. By integrating the various systems, the PCS reduces duplication of effort, saves time, and improves communication among all stakeholders. (Prasad et al., 2023)
	<u>Current Applications:</u> fourth wave of PCS, since 2018. PCS are based on multimodal service offerings, offered on the cloud and linked to other external digital logistics platforms, adopting Industry 4.0 technologies.

Vessel Traffic System (VTS)	<u>Description:</u> VTS is a maritime traffic monitoring system operated by port authorities to ensure safe and efficient vessel movements in the port area. The system uses radars, Automatic Identification System (AIS), and CCTV to track vessels in real time (Vessel Traffic Services, n.d.).
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Operators provide real-time guidance and instructions to the vessel, coordinating traffic and preventing collisions with other ships.
Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)	<u>Description:</u> RFID is a technology that uses radio waves to identify and track container movements within the port, from arrival to loading/unloading. They consist of RFID tags (small electronic devices) and RFID readers that transmit and receive radio signals (Shi, et al., 2011). They are also used in Automated Gate Operations, allowing the entry and exit of trucks and containers, and for automated data collection and paperless transactions.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> largely implemented in operational procedures in port-based container logistics. (Shi et al., 2011)
Satellite communication systems	<u>Description:</u> Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) Satellite Connectivity, MEO Satellite (GNSS) and GEO Satellites (SATCOM) provides reliable and high-speed internet access to ships operating, telecommunications, broadcasting and weather forecasting (IEC Telecom, 2023).
	<u>Current Applications:</u> While MEO and GEO are mature technologies, LEO satellites are considered relatively mature.

Table 6: Planning for arrival technologies

2. Berthing and Unberthing

Proper berthing is crucial for ensuring safety, efficiency, and the smooth operation of maritime activities. It requires coordination between the vessel's crew and port authorities, as well as consideration of factors such as tide, weather, and vessel size. By incorporating these technologies, ports can improve the efficiency and safety of berthing operations, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of maritime transport. Unberthing and departure are the concluding phases of a vessel's stay in port, marking the beginning of its voyage. These processes require careful coordination, precision, and adherence to safety protocols.

Berthing / Unberthing	
Berth Allocation System (BAS)	<p><u>Description:</u> The Berth Allocation Systems optimizes the allocation of berths to vessels, providing a solution to the Berth Allocation Problem (BAP), a logistical challenge that arises in ports when determining how to optimally allocate available berths to incoming vessels to minimize waiting times.</p> <p>Exist different categories of BAP: discrete (for berthing and unberthing), continuous, and hybrid. Many studies have focused on single quay, and few for the Multi-Quay BAP. (Aslam et al. 2023)</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> The single quay is the most used (Port of Limassol in Cyprus, has seven continuous berthing quays) while the implementation of the multiple quays is currently underway.</p>

<p>Dynamic Positioning Systems (DPS)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> DPS is an advanced technology used to maintain a vessel’s position and heading without the use of anchors making it easier to control their movements during berthing and unberthing operations. The implementation of DPS requires the vessel to be equipped with azimuth type propulsion, instead of the conventional rudder-propeller arrangement.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> DPS is currently used in special purpose vessels, such as Offshore Support Vessels, tugboats, small cargo ships.</p>
<p>Automated Berthing System (ABS)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> ABS focuses on the physical process of docking a ship by using advanced algorithms and sensors (e.g. LIDAR) onboard to help ships dock safely and efficiently using their own propulsion means.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> ABS is currently in the research and development phase with some successful pilot demonstrations of vessels berthing automatically in Europe and Japan^{1,2}.</p>
<p>Terminal Logic Control Interface (TLC)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Refers to a system or interface used to manage and control terminal activities effectively. TLC can automate several processes, such as gate operations, cargo tracking, and billing, reducing manual intervention and increasing accuracy.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> currently used in automatic stacking and automated cranes and vehicles, integrated with TOS and PCS for better coordination with stakeholders.</p>
<p>Terrestrial digital communications</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Terrestrial digital communications enable connectivity and real-time data exchange for IoT devices, machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, and user group alerting services.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-Power Wide-Area Network: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ LoRaWAN and 0G Network technology: Used to connect low-power sensors over long distances using low energy. It enables low-bandwidth, low-power communication. Ideal for IoT sensor communication that does not require high data rates, such as container location and environmental condition monitoring. ○ Cellular networks: 4G LTE and 5G connects mobile devices and sensors in real-time providing low latency and higher data speeds, ideal for more complex applications. In ports, they give access to remote control of cranes, autonomous vehicles, and real-time logistics management in the port. <p><u>Current applications:</u> Terrestrial digital communication technologies are increasingly essential in the context of ships equipped with intelligent technologies.</p>
<p>Automated Mooring Systems (AMS)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> AMS are advanced technologies used in ports to securely and efficiently moor vessels. They are essentially robotic systems that can automatically handle the process of attaching and detaching mooring lines to a vessel, or that eliminate the need for using mooring lines completely by using vacuum-based attachment methods. These systems reduce the need for manual</p>

¹ <https://www.nippon.com/en/japan-topics/g02047/>

² <https://maritime-executive.com/article/european-space-agency-sponsors-grimaldi-project-for-automated-berthing>

	<p>labour and minimize the risks associated with handling mooring lines both onboard the vessel by the Deck team and onshore and by the port stevedores.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Examples of existing AMS include Trelleborg’s³ AutoMoor™ and Cavotec’s⁴ Moormaster™ vacuum-based systems, Mampaey’s Intelligent Dock Locking System⁵ magnetic mooring system, and MacGregor’s⁶ robotic system for handling mooring lines.</p>
<p>Information Systems</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Ports are increasingly implementing systems that exploit real-time information from sensors (e.g. weather, air quality etc.) in order to facilitate decision-making in port operations.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> An example application is the Port of Rotterdam that has implemented a smart mooring solution as part of their digitalisation strategy to predict the impact that storms and adverse weather will have on moored vessels, providing users in the port with the much-needed time to prepare and avoid incidents in the port. (Port Technology International, 2021).</p>
<p>Autonomous Tugboats</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> Autonomous tugboats are highly automated vessels equipped with advanced technology, incl. sensors, computers, and propulsion systems that enable them to navigate and manoeuvre with minimal or no human intervention.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Automated tugboats are not a fully mature technology, and they are not widely implemented, although significant advancements are being made. Several industry-led projects have explored the capabilities of autonomous tugboats, including the following (Hensen, 2021):</p> <p>2017: remote control demonstration of the Svitzer Hermod in the port of Copenhagen (Rolls-Royce and Svitzer).</p> <p>2018: remote control demonstration of the Kotug RT Bocum in the port of Rotterdam from a control station in Marseille.</p> <p>2020: Intellitug project that aims to retrofit a harbour tug for enabling autonomous navigation (Wärtsilä, PSA Marine, Lloyd’s Register, the Technology Centre for Offshore and Marine Singapore (TCOMS), and co-funded by Maritime and Port Authority of Singapore’s Maritime Innovation and Technology Fund).</p> <p>2021: RECOTUG project aimed at developing a remotely controlled tugboat capable of conducting a full towage operation (Svitzer A/S, Kongsberg Maritime and ABS).</p> <p>2021: Damen designed and built tugboat Nellie Bly, outfitted with the Sea Machines Robotics autonomy system SM300, which conducted 342 collision avoidance manoeuvres during a 1000 nm voyage around Denmark while being remotely controlled from the US⁷.</p> <p>Furthermore, the EC-funded research project MOSES developed a concept for an autonomous tugboat swarm that is monitored through a remote-control station.</p>

³ <https://www.trelleborg.com/en/marine-and-infrastructure/products-solutions-and-services/marine/docking-and-mooring/automated-mooring-systems/automoor>

⁴ <https://www.cavotec.com/en/your-applications/ports-maritime/automated-mooring>

⁵ <https://twd.nl/projects/structural-design-for-mampaeys-intelligent-docklocking-system/>

⁶ <https://www.macgregor.com/intelligent-solutions/automated-mooring-system/>

⁷ <https://www.rivieramm.com/news-content-hub/news-content-hub/halfway-mark-reached-for-the-autonomous-machine-odyssey-67916>

	The project developed a machine-learning based algorithm for controlling the swarm and demonstrated the concept in a Pilot demonstration in Denmark.
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Table 7: Berthing technologies

3. Cargo Operations

Cargo operations entail the fundamental tasks of loading, unloading, storing, and handling goods aboard a vessel. Handling Units (HUs) are essential components of freight interchange nodes, facilitating the efficient transfer of cargo between different areas or modes of transportation. Automated HUs, operating without drivers, significantly enhance efficiency, flexibility, and safety. However, their implementation necessitates specialized infrastructure and skilled operators. The following section provides an overview of the latest automated HUs deployed in a container terminal (Gattuso et al., 2023).

Cargo Operations	
Automated Gantry Cranes (AGCs)	<p><u>Description:</u> Crane specialized in containers loading/unloading onto/from the ship remotely. AGCs are equipped with sensors based on laser and/or infrared technology, advanced image processing to read the codes for container identification, and information systems for crane management that define their activities in real time. The operator who controls and supervises the crane's movements is located remotely in a special room in the terminal.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> pieces of equipment for ports, enhancing efficiency, safety, and productivity. In intermodal transportation, are essential for transferring containers between different modes.</p>
Automated Straddle Carriers (ASC)	<p><u>Description:</u> The ASC allows automating the day-to-day container handling operations, improving predictability, operational efficiency and higher levels of safety. (Kalmar, n.d.)</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Straddle carrier operations are typically suited for medium-sized terminals and intermodal operations.</p>
Automated Rubber Tyred Gantry Cranes (ARTGs)	<p><u>Description:</u> Automation of Tyred Gantry Cranes can be integrated from basic crane remote control all the way to fully automated operation. In the remote-control movements, the operator controls the moves of the ARTGs from the yard control centre, while in a fully automated RTG, all crane functions and stack movements are automatic.</p> <p>Automating an existing RTG terminal is a complex, large-scale endeavour that demands extensive expertise, meticulous planning, robust systems integration capabilities, and a comprehensive approach that accounts for factors beyond just the technical aspects. (Alho et al., 2018)</p> <p>ARTGs main benefit is enhancing safety and efficiency.</p> <p><u>Current Applications</u> Approximately 60% of the world's container terminals use RTGs, although its automation requires investment and a transition long period. Dublin Ferryport Terminals implemented an automated solution to address operational challenges of the terminal. (Alho, T. et al., 2018)</p>

<p>Automatic Stacking Crane (AutoSC)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> The automated stacking crane (AutoSC) features a sophisticated optical laser system that accurately pinpoints the exact position of containers in the yard.</p> <p>With automated stacking cranes, the entire process—from container pick-up to placement, including interactions with road trucks—is fully automated.</p> <p>This advanced technology allows the ASC to position its spreader with remarkable accuracy, ensuring efficient container handling and lifting. (Automation for stacking cranes (n.d.))</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Currently more than 1.000 stacking cranes equipped with automation in more than 30 terminals worldwide.</p>
<p>Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> AGVs are unmanned, automated vehicles designed to transport material and cargo within a facility or a designated area.</p> <p>Latest generation of AGVs use advanced navigation technologies, including GNSS, camera, LiDAR- based SLAM, allowing flexible, environment-adaptive pathfinding.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> AGVs empowered with these technologies are especially useful for highly challenging environments. Ro-Ro unloading is a suitable port operation for these AGVs due to the safety, mobility and adaptability requirements.</p>
<p>Automatic Positioning Systems (APS)</p>	<p><u>Description:</u> One of the main causes of delays during container loading/unloading is the positioning of the chassis. APS improves precision, safety, and efficiency by using technologies such as GPS, sensors, cameras, and automation controls.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> DPS uses APS and is integrated in AGVs and ASCs.</p>

Table 8: Cargo operation technologies

6.1.2.2 Case studies

Case study 1: MOSES Project: *MOSES shore tugboat control station.*

Description of the project: MOSES is a H2020 funded project aimed to boost Europe’s Short Sea Shipping (SSS) supply chain by introducing a series of innovative technological developments. (CORDIS, 2024)

Overview of the case study: MOSES aimed to enhance the SSS component of the European container supply chain by reducing total time to berth for TEN-T Hub Ports and by promoting the use of SSS feeder services to small ports with limited or no infrastructure. The MOSES technological ecosystem includes an innovative SSS feeder vessel outfitted with a robotic container handling system and with the capability to dock without tug assistance, a swarm of autonomous tugboats combined with an automated mooring system for Hub Ports, and a digital collaboration platform for logistics stakeholders.

MOSES conducted three pilots in Denmark, the Netherlands, and Sweden. At the port of Faaborg in Denmark, the concept for an autonomous tugboat swarm manoeuvring a container ship to berth was demonstrated in smaller scale by employing two workboats that autonomously manoeuvred a barge to an automated mooring unit while the operation was being monitored from a remote location at the port of

Valencia, Spain. The second pilot took place in the Maritime Research Institute Netherlands (MARIN) facilities, where a scaled model was used for demonstrating the fully autonomous port-to-port operation of the innovative SSS feeder vessel. The third pilot was conducted in two locations in Sweden and the Netherlands simultaneously, which demonstrated the autonomous operation of a robotic crane installed at the premises of MacGregor while being remotely monitored by a control centre located at the premises of TNO.

Technologies used: autonomous feeder vessels, robotic container handling systems, autonomous tugboats and automated mooring systems.

Figure 4: MOSES Concept & Innovations. Source: MOSES Project. D2.2 MOSES Use Cases and scenarios

Results: MOSES project has demonstrated that autonomous and automated systems can improve supply chain efficiency, particularly in two key areas: the berthing of large containerships at container terminals and the transportation of cargo from container terminals to smaller ports. For instance, the combined use of autonomous tugboats with automated mooring systems is expected to cut the time needed to manoeuvre and dock large container ships by 25% based on the results from the pilot demonstrations previously described. (CORDIS, 2024)

These innovations collectively contribute to a safer and more efficient maritime logistics ecosystem. Such automation reduces reliance on external human resources, which is a crucial advantage for smaller ports with limited personnel or availability of tugboats and cargo handling services. Also, this advancement aligns with the broader trend of port automation, where autonomous systems optimize operations, reduce human error, and enhance safety and productivity.

Case study 2: Port of Barcelona. 5G connectivity and artificial intelligence.

Description of the port: The Port of Barcelona is a major logistics hub in the Mediterranean, and docks around 9,000 ships a year and 64 M of tones, being Spain's third largest port for international traffic. (Puertos

2023) More than 100 regular shipping lines connect it with more than 200 ports in the five continents (Port of Barcelona, n.d.).

Overview of the case study: The port has started a pilot project for testing "5G Maritime," a geolocation technology combining AI, cloud computing, 5G, and edge computing.

These technologies can complement existing tools such as AIS and geolocation radars, enhancing the data provided by current identification systems with more detailed and real-time information (5G Maritime, 2021).

The project covers the entire port area, spanning over 1,000 hectares. Leveraging the advanced capabilities of 5G networks, the solution enables high-speed data transfer, interconnection of multiple elements and sensors, and tailored coverage for Internet of Things (IoT) devices. These features ensure precise and reliable communication across the entire port (PierNext, 2022).

Technologies used: 5G connectivity, AIS, AI model and cameras with geological position radars and sensors.

Results: The implementation of this technological solution enables precise geolocation of the vessel's bow and stern, as well as real-time movement tracking. These capabilities facilitate remote navigation assistance and provide critical data for vessel entry and docking operations. By optimizing maritime traffic management, the Port of Barcelona improves both safety and sustainability in its operations (5G Maritime, 2021). Based on this study, the project lays the foundation for new use cases including security, port operations, emergency management, environmental monitoring, and sensor technology (PierNext, 2022).

Other examples

Port	Description of the case study
Port of Valencia (Spain)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The port of Valencia is the first and last port of call for regular shipping lines operating in the Western Mediterranean. As a hub for the entire Western Mediterranean, the port efficiently distributes goods, mainly containers, over a radius of 2,000 km, both in southern EU countries and in North Africa, representing a huge market of 270 million consumers (DataPorts, 2019). • Technologies Used: 5G technology • Results: The Port of Valencia tests 5G technology for ship docking operations to assist in real-time decision making and increase the safety. By using this application, masters, tugs, pilots and stevedores can know the position of the ship with millimetric precision during the entire docking phase, thus enabling more efficient decision making (Valenciaport, 2022).
Port of Shanghai (China)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: the Port of Shanghai is the world's largest automated container port. It is a crucial hub in the global shipping industry, renowned for its massive scale and efficiency, handling containers with a capacity of over 49 million twenty-foot equivalent units (TEU) annually (Intoglo, 2024). • Technologies Used: AGVs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results: The Port has implemented fully automated guided vehicles (AGVs). They have been deployed for the optimization of loading and unloading, and transportation. Equipped with wireless communication equipment and an automated dispatching system, this automated technology can move freely with precise positioning to accurately and systematically execute instructions from the central control system. (Huawei Enterprise, n.d.).
<p>MPA Singapore – Tuas Port (Singapore)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: MPA Singapore is transforming to a smarter and greener port. Tuas Port was opened in 2022 aiming to be an automated, intelligent and sustainable port. It has a handling capacity of 65 M TEUs and occupies about 1.377 ha of land (MPA, n.d.). • Technologies Used: New Generation Vessel Traffic Management System, AGVs, Automated Cranes, Autonomous tugboats. • Results: This technology is being implemented in order to provide accurate, real-time situational awareness of the shipping traffic and enhancing efficiency of port operations and reduce the turnaround time of ships. Also, lower carbon emissions by implementing electrified equipment (MPA, n.d.).

Table 9: Use Case 1, Case Studies

6.1.3 User needs and technological gaps

This section will delve into the specific user needs associated with vessel port call operations and how the automation framework proposed for this UC will address them, as well as the technological gaps that must be bridged to implement the automation concept. The users that are relevant to this specific operation/process include the port, the vessel operator, the tugboat owner/operator, and the logistics providers.

USER NEEDS	
OPERATIONAL NEEDS	
<p>Minimize delays</p>	<p>Description: The manoeuvring and mooring process may be delayed, e.g. due to miscommunication between tugboats and vessel pilots, leading to lack of coordination, and lost time for securing mooring lines respectively.</p> <p>Need for solution: Autonomous tugboats will eliminate the need for the pilot on the vessel to coordinate their movements and therefore the service will be more efficient. Automated mooring systems eliminate the need for using mooring ropes and therefore significantly reduce the time required for securing the vessel to berth.</p>
<p>Improve safety</p>	<p>Description: The factors that affect human safety during the manoeuvring process include miscommunication between tugboats and vessel pilot, human errors due to fatigue and stress. Furthermore, involved personnel are</p>

	<p>at risk considering the possibility of accidents, such as girting. The mooring process involves several risks for the vessel deck team and the port stevedores related to the use of mooring ropes.</p> <p>Need for solution: The reduced involvement of humans in the operation of autonomous tugboats results in less people being exposed to risk during the manoeuvring process. Furthermore, eliminating the need for mooring ropes removes the associated hazards and risks.</p>
Minimize port air emissions	<p>Description: When assisted by tugboats, vessels do not use their own propulsion means, and therefore the main contributor of air emissions during the manoeuvring process are tugboat movements.</p> <p>Need for solution: Autonomous tugboats are expected to be more efficient in terms of the time required to berth the vessel and therefore have less emissions compared to conventional tugboats (assuming the same type of engine used).</p>
MANAGEMENT NEEDS	
Real-time process monitoring	<p>Description: Data exchanges between towed vessel, tugboats, and the port related to the progress of the operation, incl. the positions and speeds of the tugboats and the towed vessel, status of the mooring arrangements.</p> <p>Need for solution: The operation of autonomous tugboats combined with automated mooring systems will require acquiring the information related to the progress of the process, which can be relayed to the digital port systems for ensuring real-time monitoring.</p>
Provision of 24/7 port services	<p>Description: Personnel working hours and resource limitations (e.g. tugboats, mooring equipment, etc.) due to increased port traffic results in the tugboat assistance and mooring port services not being offered continuously.</p> <p>Need for solution: Autonomous tugboats and automated mooring systems are expected to reduce manoeuvring and docking times, while minimizing the involvement of relevant personnel, resulting in increasing the amount of traffic the port can handle.</p>

Table 10: User needs of UC1

The following are technological gaps related to the integration of autonomous tugboats within the port call process, which are mainly owed to the inherent operational complexity and the need to communicate with other involved actors.

TECH GAPS	
Interaction of autonomous tugboats with conventional vessels	<p>Description: The autonomous tugboats will operate in a confined area with other conventional vessels and therefore need to react to their movements, as well as exchange operational information when needed.</p> <p>Impact: In case autonomous tugboats do not react to the movement of other vessels in the area, there is a risk of collision. In case autonomous tugboats do</p>

	not exchange information, other vessels will not be aware of the intentions of the autonomous tugboats.
Data exchange rate and management for real-time process monitoring	<p>Description: The operation of the autonomous tugboats needs to be continuously monitored, which involves transmitting a large amount of information to the shore through a stable connection. This data also needs to be managed on shore with respect to storage and maintaining an adequate situational awareness for the monitoring agent.</p> <p>Impact: Transmitting all the necessary information may lead to overloading the wireless connection. Furthermore, if the monitoring agent does not have an adequate understanding of the progress of the operation, then their capabilities to intervene in case of failures will be limited.</p>
Cyber security issues	<p>Description: Vulnerabilities related to the need for the systems involved (i.e. autonomous tugboats, shore control, automated mooring system) to be wirelessly connected (e.g. to share information, to transfer control to the remote operator, etc.).</p> <p>Impact: Vulnerabilities may be exploited by external actors, e.g. to take over control of the autonomous tugboats, or disrupt their operation.</p>

Table 11: Technological GAPS, Use Case 1

6.1.4 Use Case Scenarios

As described previously in section 6.1, UC1 will be focused on and will simulate the port call process, i.e. berthing and unberthing of vessels. The process consists of a specific sequence of events, which are shown in Figure 5: The sequence of events for the berthing and unberthing process, and described below:

1. The vessel is anchored at the designated location within the port where it will meet the tugboats.
2. The tugboats autonomously navigate from their berthing point to the designated meeting point, where the vessel is located.
3. The personnel onboard the tugboats secure the towing lines to the vessel and take their initial positions along the length of the vessel.
4. Once all tugboats are in position, the autonomous manoeuvring process to berth the vessel process begins.
5. Once the autonomous tugboats have manoeuvred the vessel to a specific point near the quay, the Automated Mooring System (AMS) is activated and initiates the mooring sequence.
6. Once the vessel is securely moored at berth, the cargo operations (UC2) commence.⁸

⁸ The connection between UC 1 and UC 2 is as follows: A signal will be transmitted once the vessel is securely moored (UC 1). Upon receiving this signal, UC 2 (cargo operations) may commence. Once the cargo operations are finalised, another signal will be transmitted. Upon the transmission of this signal, the unberthing process will commence. Cargo operations are independent of the berthing and unberthing processes, as they cannot be performed simultaneously.

7. Upon the finalisation of the cargo operations (UC2), the unberthing process starts in an opposite sequence of the events:
 - a. The tugboats autonomously navigate from their berthing point to the berth, where the vessel is located.
 - b. The personnel onboard the tugboats secure the towing lines to the berthed vessel and take their initial positions along the length of the vessel.
 - c. Once all tugboats are in position, the Automated Mooring System (AMS) is deactivated and the autonomous manoeuvring process to unberth the vessel process begins.
 - d. Once the vessel is manoeuvred to a dedicated point in the port area where, it can navigate without the need of the tugboats, the towing lines are released, and the vessel start its route.

Figure 5: The sequence of events for the berthing and unberthing process

For the Use Case scenarios, the following assumptions will be made:

- **Vessel type**
 - The manoeuvred vessel will be a conventional containership (i.e. with crew onboard). From the perspective of harbour tugboat operations, containerships are considered as a “worst-case” scenario for the following reasons: 1) containerships have a large windage area compared to other cargo vessels (comparable to passenger and cruise ships), which increases the total required bollard pull as a function of the wind intensity and the number of tugboats required for the operation, and 2) containerships operate in the liner shipping market, which means that their operation is time-sensitive in terms of the duration of the berthing and cargo operations phases.
- **Port**

- The environment where the operation will be assumed to take place will be a generic container terminal with a generic layout that will be generated from existing ports servicing containerships.
- The quays of the port terminal will be equipped with an Autonomous Mooring System (AMS) that does not require the use of mooring lines.
- **Tugboats**
 - The tugboats will be fully autonomous in terms of navigation functions (i.e. no master onboard). The only crew onboard the vessel will be seafarers for deploying and securing the towing lines between the vessel and the tugboat.
 - The tugboats' autonomous functions will be monitored by an operator in a Shore Control Centre within the port premises.
 - The tugboats' propulsion system will be fully electric with an Azimuth Stern Drive (ASD).

Key Variables and Parameters

The key parameters that will be considered in the simulation are shown below, along with a brief description on the way they influence the whole process:

- **Environmental conditions**
 - Wind speed increases the air resistance due to the vessel's large windage area, hence the total bollard pull required for manoeuvring the vessel and consequently the number of tugboats that will be assigned to manoeuvre vessel.
 - Wave height affects both the tugboats and the vessel movements, as higher wave heights require greater bollard pull to manoeuvre the vessel. Furthermore, wave height has an effect on the efficiency of the nominal bollard pull of every tugboat.
 - Sea currents increase water resistance especially when their direction is lateral to the vessel's movement, which can affect both the overall process and the tugboats' movement.
- **Vessel**
 - The size of vessel impacts the overall process, as a larger vessel results in a greater windage and wetted surface areas, requiring more or stronger tugboats to manoeuvre the vessel.
 - Thrusters: The total power of the installed bow and/or stern thrusters on the manoeuvred vessel, as well as whether they are operational or not, affect the total required bollard pull as well as the number of tugboats that must be assigned for the process.
 - Number of tugboats used to manoeuvre the vessel, which is a function of the above-mentioned parameters.

The following are the key variables that can be utilised to indicate the efficiency of the overall process and to evaluate the scenarios:

- Total time for completing the manoeuvring operation.
- Number of tugboat movements.

It should be highlighted that other indicators may be identified during the development of the Use Case.

The Use Case will include the following two main groups of scenarios where the key parameters will vary:

- Containership with all thrusters operational in good and heavy weather.
- Containership with some thrusters operational in good and heavy weather.

The narrative as well as the overall process for both scenarios remain the same, however below there is a short description for both scenarios.

6.1.4.1 Scenario 1: Containership with all thrusters operational in good and heavy weather

This first group of scenarios will simulate the berthing and unberthing process of a specific containership where all vessel thrusters are considered operational. The weather conditions will vary across the different sub-scenarios, categorised in good (i.e. wind speed up to 4 Beaufort and wave heights less than 1.0 m) and heavy weather (i.e. wind speed between 5 and 6 Beaufort and wave heights greater than 1.0 m).

6.1.4.2 Scenario 2: Containership with thrusters not operational in good and heavy weather

The second group of scenarios will simulate the berthing and unberthing process of the same containership as in Scenario 1, but with the vessel's thrusters operating either partially or not at all. The weather conditions will follow the same rationale as in Scenario 1, with variations across the different sub-scenarios, categorised as either good or heavy weather.

6.1.5 Concept of Operations (ConOps)

6.1.5.1 Current Operational Environment

Planning for arrival phase

The containership calls the pilot via VHF during the port call execution process. The pilot plans how the vessel will approach the berth and contacts the harbour tugboat services, while waiting for the port to allocate an appropriate slot for the vessel. Once the berth has been allocated, the vessel waits at the designated pilot boarding position and the tugboats assigned by the tugboat operator move towards the location where they will meet the vessel and await instructions from the pilot. Once the tugboats and vessel are in position and the tow lines to the vessel have been secured by the onboard personnel, the manoeuvring operation commences.

Berthing phase

The tugboats manoeuvre the vessel towards the target position in the allocated berth by executing the commands provided by the pilot on the vessel, who is in continuous communication with the tugboat Captains to coordinate the movements of the tugboats. Once the vessel has been positioned at the berthing position, the mooring process commences for securing the vessel at its berth, during which the mooring team onboard the vessel coordinates with the port stevedores.

6.1.5.2 Proposed Operational Model

Planning for arrival phase

The vessel waits for the port to allocate a berth. The autonomous tugboats receive a mission profile from the Berth Allocation System (BAS), which includes the vessel characteristics, the location where they will

meet the vessel, and the location of the allocated berth. The mission profile is also sent to the Automated Mooring System (AMS) that is positioned at the allocated berth. The autonomous tugboats meet the vessel at the designated location and the tow lines are secured by the onboard personnel. Once the secure connection between the tugboats and the vessel has been verified, the autonomous manoeuvring process commences.

Berthing phase

During the autonomous manoeuvring process, the operation is remotely monitored by a shore-based operator in-the-loop (i.e. with the possibility to intervene for operational or safety reasons). During the autonomous operation, the pilot will not actively participate but monitor out-of-the-loop (i.e. without the possibility to intervene). The Automated Mooring System (AMS) will be automatically triggered by the autonomous tugboats when the vessel has been verified to be in the berthing position. After the mooring process is successfully completed, the AMS notifies the autonomous tugboats to disengage.

6.1.5.3 Data Flows and Interactions

Figure 6 illustrates how different components and stakeholders involved in the automation framework exchange information and data during the automated berthing and unberthing process.

Figure 6: Diagram of interactions between components in the automation framework

6.2 UC2 : Automated port operations

6.2.1 Use Case definition

6.2.1.1 Purpose and Scope

The UC2 focuses on demonstrating the benefits of automating port terminal processes through simulation. It will integrate historical data with a high-reliable simulation model to replicate current baseline operations performance with aspirations of being compared to its automated counterpart. Hence, the simulation will assess various operational objectives, showcasing how automation might improve aspects of terminal, such as vessel handling, cargo operations, vehicle flow, and logistics efficiency.

By simulating these scenarios, the platform aims to achieve an optimal configuration of the terminal operations that reduces inefficiencies, lowers environmental impact, and enhances synchronization within the logistics chain. Ultimately, the simulation enables comprehensive forecasting, offering valuable insights into the potential impact of automation on port terminal performance, whereas remaining scalability and transferability to other terminals on intermodality framework.

6.2.1.2 General Overview of the Use Case

Use case 2 aims to provide the port with a simulation environment that allows it to assess the economic and execution time benefits of applying certain automation to its logistics processes, to determine whether the application of such automation is appropriate without incurring the costs and inconveniences of carrying out a real feasibility test on-site. Among the variety of activities that take place in port terminal operations, this use case will focus on the operations encompassing from the arrival of the vessel to the storage of the cargo. The following main processes will be simulated:

- Loading and Unloading
- Transfer of cargo to the warehouse
- Cargo handling and shunting operations
- Warehouse operations

Although these are the main events to be simulated in the use case, each of them also involves a wide range of other minor processes which for simplification purposes are included in the corresponding main process.

6.2.2 State-of-the-Art analysis of automated port operations

Port operations play a key role in the freight logistics chain. This is because ports, as an intermodal node, represent an important part of global freight transport. Therefore, improving the efficiency of port operations becomes a necessity to meet future market demands.

Nevertheless, port terminals are intermodal nodes with high complexity and heterogeneity throughout the whole spectrum. Due to these conditions surrounding port operations, it is necessary to comprehend the different typologies of terminals that exist to subsequently be able to examine the state of the art that best reflects the Bilbao Port use case. The following classification shows the variety of port terminals according to purpose and type of cargo:

Figure 7: Port terminal classification

A single purpose terminal is a specialized terminal for handling unique cargoes. This type of terminal has unique economic appeal and uses special types of equipment for maximum throughput. Whereas a multipurpose terminal can be defined as a complex of infrastructure, equipment and services which offers a combined and flexible response to the servicing demand of certain types of vessels and cargo, permitting the optimum utilization of manpower and equipment. (Enriquez, 1991)

Different types of freight port terminals have certain features that confer them the ability to reach a much higher level of systematization and standardization, consequently a greater capacity to integrate a high degree of terminal automation. Martin-Soberón et al., in 2014, resume these features as:

- The standardisation of the means of transport
- The standardisation of the way freight is handled
- The high level of interchanges taking places
- The high impact of technology on the profitability of terminals

Implementing automation in terminals differs significantly between greenfield (newly built) terminals and brownfield terminals. While greenfield terminals can be designed and automated from the outset, brownfield terminals require a phased transition, implemented gradually in different areas to prevent any loss of capacity. In this context, levels of automation in a port terminal can be categorized based on the degree of human intervention required and the sophistication of the technology used (Rodriguez et al. 2021):

- **Fully Automated Terminal:** Minimal human intervention is needed, focusing primarily on remote monitoring, system supervision, and equipment maintenance.
- **Highly Automated Terminal:** Automation covers most processes, but human oversight is required for non-standard or complex scenarios.

- **Partially Automated Terminal:** Select processes are automated, often to streamline repetitive or predictable tasks. Human operators perform critical and complex functions, while automation supports efficiency in basic operations.
- **Semi-Automated Terminal:** Automation is minimal and only applied in specific, isolated processes. The focus remains on manual control, with automation serving as an aid rather than replacing human roles.

In the case of Bilbao Port is a multipurpose (brownfield) terminal which handles bulk, containerized, Ro-Ro and general cargo. Terminals of this nature prioritize high flexibility to different vessel types, often at the expense of standardization. In this particular use case, the focus is on enhancing the Ro-Ro operations by moving from a 'semi-automated' setup - where automation aids specific manual tasks - to a 'partially automated' model.

Current research on port operations automation is primarily focused on containerized cargo due to its standardization in the means of transport and handling equipment. However, there lacks extensive research on Ro-Ro terminals because the involved operations are challenging to carry out in an unmanned or mechanized form, so the current Ro-Ro system is heavily dependent on human resources. (Park et al. 2021) Yet, the vast majority of advances in Ro-Ro unloading have been developed in the implementation of AGVs that are capable of autonomously and safely navigate inside the ship and transferring the cargo to the dockside. AGVs first generation vehicles were designed to navigate according to line-following principles using technologies such as embedded guide wires, paint stripes, magnetic tape, and laser guidance. The development of intelligent autonomous vehicles (IAVs) and automated lifting vehicles (ALVs) has alleviated the limitations to navigate through any environment. This new generation of autonomous vehicles applicable to Ro-Ro unloading uses Global Navigation System, camera, LiDAR-based simultaneous localization and mapping technologies for pathfinding.

The following phases represent the main port operations at a Ro-Ro terminal:

Figure 8: Ro-Ro terminal port operations phases

PREVIOUS TO SHIP ARRIVAL	
Phase	Description
Documentation	The essential documents and logistic details need to be prepared for a proper planning orchestration prior to the ship's arrival. These processes are the following:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stowing Plan: This plan details the cargo layout inside the ship, helping optimize the unloading process. • Packing List: A comprehensive list of all cargo items, used for verifying accuracy upon unloading. • Ship Arrival Schedule: Precise day and time of arrival.
Planning & Resource Allocation	Plans and coordinates the timing of port operations and events to avoid conflicts and delays. In parallel, assigns and distributes resources (vehicles, equipment, and personnel) to operations based on the planning to fulfill performance and schedule requirements.
ARRIVAL OF THE SHIP	
Phase	Description
Reception	<p>In the reception phase, resources and equipment reach out the dockside to initiate the unloading from the vessel using the Ro-Ro ramp. This phase consists of the following processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Truck enters the vessel using the Ro-Ro ramp. • Drives to where the cargo is located inside the ship using the stowage plan as reference. • Couple the truck to the loaded trailer. • Drives outside the vessel. • Place the loaded trailer on the designated unloading area.
Cargo Transfer	Refers to the process of transporting cargo within port facilities from one place to another. However, this process is related to the specific cargo transfer carried out from the reception to the warehouse designated area. Conversely, during dispatch, it entails transferring consolidated cargo from the warehouse to the loading zone in preparation for outbound transport.
Warehousing	<p>Refers to the set of procedures carried out within the warehouse facilities. Before the final storage a variety of pre-requirements are carried out to ensure the successful control and management over the cargo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cargo Identification • Material Inspection • Storage area preparation <p>Once the pre-requirement procedures are executed, the cargo is prepared to be stored in its designated location. The required operators and equipment proceed with the cargo shunting operations to store the cargo in its designated final location.</p> <p>Finally, the cargo is retrieved from its location upon request. In order to efficiently retrieve the cargo, the warehouse management system provides the required</p>

	information, such as, cargo identification number, store location reference, and destination.
Dispatching	The dispatching phase involves preparing and moving outbound cargo from the warehouse to the loading zone for final transport. This phase includes consolidating and organizing cargo based on transport schedules, verifying cargo readiness, and coordinating the necessary equipment and resources to efficiently load the cargo onto the outbound vessel or transport vehicle. Accurate documentation and inventory checks are performed to ensure that the correct cargo is dispatched, minimizing delays and maintaining a smooth flow of operations for departure.

Table 12: Ro-Ro terminal port operations phases description

6.2.2.1 Current Technology state

Documentation	
Terminal Operating System (TOS)	Description: The TOS is a software that manages all loading and unloading operations, coordinates equipment actions and support human actions and controls.
	Current Applications: TOS is a mature technology, and has a fundamental role in improving operational efficiency, reducing costs, and optimizing the supply chain in maritime logistics. Some examples are SYSTRA in Rotterdam, NAVIS N4 in Los Angeles or PortXChange in Hamburg.
Port Community Systems (PCS)	Description: see the section 6.1.2.1
	Current Applications: see the section 6.1.2.1
Document Visual Analysis	Description: Document processing is a complex technology that must be adapted to its means. In port operations, a combination of techniques such as optical character recognition (OCR) and natural language processing (NLP)- AI empowered algorithm – can interpret the documents. Finally, APIs are responsible for embedding this information into the correspondent equipment.
	Current Applications: Document recognition and processing technology is widely used to transform documents, such as the stowage plan, into an interpretable language by the AGVs so that they can navigate the ship based on specific criteria and guidelines.
Planning and Resource Allocation	
Resource Management Systems	Description: Software solutions that track and allocate resources. Personnel, vehicles and equipment can be systemized to optimize operational efficiency.

	Current Applications: Used in port operations to optimally distribute workforce equipment and qualified personnel for each task.
Predictive Dynamic Decision Support	Description: Software that provides real-time insights and analytics to support decision-making under uncertainty and condition changes.
	Current Applications: Predictive resource allocation based on historical data, performance and KPIs for future events. Through the gathered data and insights, transform information into high-impact decision making.
Reception	
Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV)	Description: AGVs are unmanned, automated vehicles designed to transport material and cargo within a facility or a designated area. Latest generation of AGVs use advanced navigation technologies, including GNSS, camera, LiDAR-based SLAM, allowing flexible, environment-adaptive pathfinding.
	Current Applications: AGVs empowered with these technologies are especially useful for highly challenging environments. Ro-Ro unloading is a suitable port operation for these AGVs due to the safety, mobility and adaptability requirements.
Automated Lifting Vehicles (ALV)	Description: ALVs are automated vehicles designed specifically to lift and transport heavy cargo. They are equipped with hydraulic and sensor-based systems.
	Current Applications: During the Ro-Ro unloading process are used primarily to efficiently lift and stack the cargo from the ground level to the trailer and vice versa.
Automated Coupling Systems	Description: Automated systems that facilitate seamless connection and disconnection between transport vehicles and trailers, using sensors and electromechanical systems
	Current Applications: Applied in reception processes to ensure safe and efficient attachment/detachment of loaded trailers and cargo units.
AGV Communication System	Description: Refers to a networked system enabling the AGV fleet to communicate among different vehicles. AGV Communication Systems use radio frequency-based technologies to support connectivity. Depending on the specific requirements diverse latency, wave beam, and coverage specifications must be fulfilled.
	Current Applications: Support AGVs in Ro-Ro unloading operations by allowing real-time route adjustments, task synchronization, and collision avoidance.
Cargo Transfer	
Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV)	Description: see the section 6.1.2.1
	Current Applications: see the section 6.1.2.1
Warehousing	

Material Inspection	
Radio Frequency Identification (RFID)	Description: see the section 6.1.2.1
	Current Applications: see the section 6.1.2.1
Visual Analytics	Description: Advanced camera systems combined with machine vision supported by AI for real-time identification.
	Current Applications: Visual Analytic cameras are employed in a wide range of applications such as cargo identification, object classification, presence/absence check, defect detection, high-level quality control.
Dron-based Surveillance	Description: Unmanned aerial vehicles equipped with cameras and sensors for aerial surveillance and tracking of inventory within large storage facilities.
	Current Applications: Used for quick, high-level inspection of storage areas and hard-to-reach inventory locations in warehouses. This technology also is suitable for high-level quality inspection, such as packaging rips, water filtrations, crack detection, etc.
Storage Area Preparation	
Inventory Management Systems	Description: Software-based solutions integrating real-time data from various sources (e.g., TOS data, RFID, scanners) to manage stock levels and track storage locations.
	Current Applications: Applied to optimize storage space allocation and ensure real-time tracking of inventory movements in warehouses. It is also widely used to precisely and rapidly identify specific cargo location and status.
Shunting Operations	
Automated Storage and Retrieval Systems (AS/RS)	Description: An Automated Storage and Retrieval System (ASRS) is engineered to optimize inventory management by automating essential tasks such as storage, picking, and replenishment. This system utilizes advanced technologies, including specialized software, computer systems, and robotics, to simplify and enhance the processes of handling, storing, and retrieving items in a warehouse setting. (Gonzalez, 2024)
	Current Applications: AS/RS has been implemented across various sectors that require optimal storage management.
Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV)	Description: Most warehouse AGVs use simple line-following technologies, like embedded guide wires or magnetic tape, to move goods along fixed paths. In warehouses with structured layouts, such as corridors and cells, AGVs follow predefined routes, so advanced technology is often unnecessary beyond what is needed for basic safety.
	Current Applications: Suitable for controlled storage environments. The main applications are related to autonomously moving boxes, pallets or cargo between different designated storage zones. Recently AGV warehouse fleets

	are used to autonomously reorganize optimally the storage besides principal uses related to picking, moving, and relocating cargo.
Automated Lifting Vehicles (ALV)	Description: ALVs are automated vehicles designed specifically to lift and transport heavy cargo. They are equipped with hydraulic and sensor-based systems to enable precise cargo handling.
	Current Applications: ALVs in warehouse shunting operations are particularly useful to autonomously and safely manipulate, handle, pick, move, and relocate cargo.

Table 13: Current technologies of Ro-Ro terminal operations

6.2.2.2 Case Studies

Port Community System (PCS) in Port of Hamburg

Description: Port of Hamburg is the largest seaport in Germany and the third largest container port in Europe. Around 6,900 container ships and more than 7.7 million TEU were handled in 2023. (Dakosy, n.d.)

Overview of the Case Study: The increasing number of ships that must be handled within short time slots requires a forward-thinking, digital exchange of cargo-related information between the involved parties and authorities, ensuring smooth and timely operations for pre- and on-carriage of containers by intermodal transporters. To address this need, the Port has implemented the Port Community System (PCS) technology, which connects over 2,000 enterprises and authorities, being one of the world's most advanced digital port community platforms.

As previously described, the primary goal of a PCS is to streamline port operations by enabling paperless transactions. It achieves this through a unified platform that facilitates the exchange of essential port-related information and documents, such as customs data, import/export declarations, transport orders, and hazardous goods reports. The Port of Hamburg platform is composed of four main components: Port call, import/export, and hinterland. Specifically, in the port call module, PCS continuously reports ship positions and calculates timeframes, which are crucial for optimizing ship management and coordination on the Elbe River and within the port.

Technologies used: Advanced Software for the Port Community System (PCS)

Results: The implementation of the Port Community System (PCS) has enhanced integration, full transparency and real-time data access for the ecosystem. (Dakosy, n.d.). PCS accelerates the flow of goods through the Port of Hamburg's supply chains by enabling faster and more transparent handling processes across its four main modules. This system benefits all stakeholders, including companies and authorities, by streamlining operations. These interfaces enable swift data exchange between dispatchers, the Port of Hamburg, international recipients, and back again. This efficient communication system ensures smooth logistical operations, contributing to optimized supply chain performance (Kapkaeva et al., 2021).

Figure 9: Import and Export processes to automation. Source: from Kapkaeva, et al. (2021)

Manzanillo International Terminal. Panama

Description: The International Terminal of Manzanillo is a port located to the east of the Atlantic entrance of the Panama Canal. It is one of the largest container transshipment terminals in the region, with direct access to the Colón Free Zone (ZLC). The International Terminal of Manzanillo has a 3 km long access channel and a depth of 14 m. This allows for manoeuvrability and the capability to receive all types of vessels, making it a port with world-class facilities. Therefore, it has modern and systematic installations. (Ssamarine, n.d.)

Overview of the case study: MIT Panama implements optical character recognition (OCR) to automate data collection. This technology has been implemented in all its ship-to-shore (STS) cranes, to automate information capture for containers. The new set-up includes recognition capability, leveraging artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning technologies to enhance read rates. The centralised data delivered by the system will be used to improve planning at the berth and throughout the terminal handling process.

Technologies used: Optical character recognition (OCR), STS Cranes

Results: MIT Panama has automated data collection to enhance the efficiency of operations, which is crucial in high-traffic areas where even minor delays can cause significant backlogs. Also implementing OCR technology will minimize human errors in data entry, reducing the risk of miscommunication, delays, and incorrect shipments. (O'Dwyer, 2022)

→Others

Port	Description of the case study
Port of Rotterdam (Netherlands)	Overview: The Port of Rotterdam is the largest port in Europe, with a throughput of approximately 470 million tonnes of freight per year. The port of Rotterdam is

	<p>making its physical infrastructure and assets smarter, becoming one of the most innovative and smarter ports in the world. (Castelein, n.d.)</p> <p>Technologies used: Sensors and real-time data, AI, Machine Learning, smart mooring line load, among others.</p> <p>Results: Sensors monitors and communicates with the state of assets in real time, this allows the port to take measures at the right time for the best possible lifespan. By using AI, the port instructs computers to recognise anomalies for automating asset inspection. Smart mooring helps to monitoring the load in real time and better understand which vessels can berth at which quays. (Port of Rotterdam, n.d.)</p>
<p>Port of Antwerp (Belgium)</p>	<p>Overview: Port of Antwerp, in Belgium, is the second largest port in Europe, and it connects the European continent to the rest of the world. Cargo ships of all shapes and sizes, not only containers, pass through this port. Containers, RORO cargo, dry bulk and tankers with liquid products, heavy-lifts and breakbulk ships. (Port of Antwerp Bruges, n.d.)</p> <p>Technologies used: horizontal twin lift for wind turbine cargo</p> <p>Results: As it is mentioned, the Port of Antwerp handles all types of transport. Unloading the ship of turbine cargo, the port uses two reach stackers with an 80-ton capacity, each piece of cargo is moved to the stacking area further down the quay. During all operations, the cargo agent is present on the quay to check the cargo. This example reflects the lack of automation in non-container cargo operations, and still has room for technological maturity and implementation. (Port of Antwerp Bruges, n.d.)</p>
<p>Port of Shanghai (China)</p>	<p>Overview: the Port of Shanghai is the world’s largest automated container port. The Port of Shanghai is a crucial hub in the global shipping industry, renowned for its massive scale and efficiency. However, has implemented an efficient automatic bulk loading and unloading, along with achieving management and control integration of automated operations creatively, and establishing a solid foundation for building fully automatic bulk cargo terminals.</p> <p>Technologies used: long-distance materials detection, computer network, automatic control, intelligent decision-making, grab anti-sway, path planning, video surveillance, and remote monitoring equipment (Qifan, 2019)</p> <p>Results: Accurate positioning of the cargo, achieving uniform loading, and increasing the operating efficiency. These technologies will improve management and control integration of automated operations creatively, and establishing a solid foundation for building fully automatic bulk cargo terminals.</p>

Table 14: Description of case studies UC2

6.2.3 User needs and technological gaps

In this use case, Toro and Betolaza (terminal operators) and Port of Bilbao (port authorities) have specific requirements that must be met to enhance the efficiency, safety, and reliability of shunting processes.

This section will delve into the specific user needs associated with automated port operations, as well as the technological gaps that must be bridged to enhance overall performance and drive progress in the maritime sector.

General user needs:

- Lack of coordination between the arrival/departure of ships and reception by the vehicles at the dock leading to high downtime.
- Manually executed operations leading to extended idle times and human errors, such as, inspections in reception and warehouse
- Inefficiencies in planning of cargo reception, transfer and storage, due to lack of reliable information.

The classification of specific user needs was developed following the general user requirements defined by Toro & Betolaza and the Port of Bilbao. Furthermore, an additional distinction was made between operational and management requirements, reflecting the inherent characteristics of each need.

OPERATIONAL NEEDS	
Reception Operations	
Optimize & Coordinate Loading and Unloading	<p>Description: these operations seek to optimize both operational times and idle times to reduce berth occupancy and increase reception efficiency.</p> <p>Need for solution: unloading and loading are executed sequentially by operators. Automate and synchronize these operations might have a significant impact.</p>
Warehouse Operations	
Material Inspection	<p>Description: once the cargo is unloaded from the vessel, cargo specifications are checked against the delivery note and quality control are performed.</p> <p>Need for solution: material inspection is a quite standardized and monotonous process. The dependency of manual labor for this task can lead to human errors and entail a time and resource waste.</p>
Shunting Operations	<p>Description: primarily refers to operations involving cargo handling equipment, such as, forklift cargo maneuvering, Ro-Ro transfer, cargo replacement, etc.</p> <p>Need for solution: shunting operations performed by automated equipment could increase safety, efficiency and control.</p>
Storage & Retrieval Optimization	<p>Description: systems dedicated to store, organize, and retrieve goods efficiently within a warehouse.</p> <p>Need for solution: enhance inventory management, cargo monitoring, space optimization, reduce retrieval and storage times.</p>

Transportation	
Cargo Transfer	<p>Description: in port terminals context is defined as the process of transferring cargo from the vessel to the warehouse.</p> <p>Need for solution: reduce accidents, waiting times, suboptimal route selection and continuous service.</p>
MANAGEMENT NEEDS	
Resource Allocation	<p>Description: assigns and distributes resources (vehicles, equipment, and personnel) to operations based on planning to fulfill performance and schedule requirements.</p> <p>Need for solution: ensure optimal resource use, minimize downtime, and reduce bottlenecks.</p>
Event Scheduling	<p>Description: plans and coordinates the timing of port operations and events to avoid conflicts and delays.</p> <p>Need for solution: achieve seamless workflow between connected port operations by preventing congestion and avoid cascade effect.</p>
Dynamic Decision Support	<p>Description: provides real-time insights and analytics to support decision-making under uncertainty and condition changes.</p> <p>Need for solution: adapt quickly to changing situations, improve response time and minimize the impact of disruptions.</p>
Synchronization	<p>Description: refers to the coordination of timing and events occurring in a reduced time lapse.</p> <p>Need for solution: minimize idle times and improve overall workflow efficiency</p>

Table 15: User Needs, Use Case 2

Despite substantial progress in port operations, several gaps persist that limit full optimization within port terminals. Recognizing these technological gaps is essential for stakeholders aiming to improve efficiency, safety, and reliability. The main gaps identified include:

TECH GAPS	
Monitoring	<p>Description: tracking of equipment and cargo in the port terminal. Devices like IoT sensors, RFID tags, embedded cameras and lasers are commonly used for monitoring purposes.</p> <p>Impact: helps gaining control over equipment status, location, and operational flows. This control enables port operators to respond rapidly to issues, reduce equipment downtime, and provide insights. Ultimately, effective monitoring contributes to smoother, more reliable operations, lower costs, and transparency.</p>
Software Challenges	<p>Description: the automation of infrastructures, vehicles, equipment, and operations require sophisticated programmed logic that provides this hardware to behave, respond and operate as expected.</p>

	Impact: non-adequate powered automation may derive in poor decision making, unexpected functionalities, and safety commitment issues.
Data Integration, consistency and management	Description: refers to the practice of collecting, keeping, and sharing data securely, efficiently, and cost-effectively across the systems that compose the data management ecosystem. Impact: the integration of seamless data flow allows to maximize actions benefit by providing accurate and relevant information. Moreover, ensures sensitive information is protected from cyberattacks.
Infrastructure limitations	Description: physical and technical constraints within the port, including equipment, network devices, warehouse rack systems, sensors, vehicles, roads, trailers, etc. Impact: may hinder automation, limit scalability, decelerate implementation, and increase return on investment
Demand Forecasting	Description: utilization of historical and real-time data to predict future events, execution times, unexpected circumstances, and reaction capabilities among others. Impact: enables proactive resource allocation, reduce bottlenecks and cascade effects, and improve scheduling accuracy.

Table 16: Technological Gaps, Use Case 2

6.2.4 Use Case Scenarios

6.2.4.1 Scenario 1: Paper Reels Logistics

Narrative Description

The steps to be followed for the scenario are the following:

1. Comprehend and define the discrete processes involved in the use case framework.
2. Identify the entities, actors, and resources required for each process.
3. Establish the fundamental relations among the entities and events.
4. Outline the Logical flowchart of the scenario – Logistic Pipeline definition.
5. Recognize specific KPIs that unearth the preconceived inefficiencies related to the user needs.
6. Build a Digital Twin (Reference Architecture for Digital Twins) which enables to represent accurately the baseline performance.
7. Introduce required automation elements on the identified processes to bridge the technological and efficiency gaps.
8. Simulate automation alternatives based on what-if scenarios. These automated scenario assumptions must belong to main event blocks of the logistic pipeline; such as, loading and unloading, warehousing, operations planning, and transfer.
9. Calculate corresponding KPIs for each scenario.
10. Comparison of the KPIs of each automated scenario with the baseline.

Key Variables and Parameters

- Unloading cargo specifications
 - Number of Paper reels
 - Number of trailers for unloading
- Workforce Capabilities
 - Number of Specialized Personnel
 - Number of Available Machinery
- Infrastructure Features
 - Ro-Ro ramp width
 - Internal Road Congestion
- Vessel arrival rate
- Re-scheduling parameters

6.2.5 Concept of Operations (ConOps)

6.2.5.1 Current Operational Environment

From an overall perspective of port terminal logistic pipeline, all involved processes can be coupled in 7 main event blocks. The chronological workflow classification of these event blocks obeys the following structure:

Planning & Documentation

Arrival

Reception

Warehousing

Dispatching

Departure

Transportation

As it is noted on the “General Logistic Pipeline” represented on the Figure 10, the transportation block is considered a transversal process with interleaved presence throughout the workflow.

Arising from the defined events blocks of the “General Logistic Pipeline”, the underlying processes of the paper reels logistic operations can be associated to its correspondent generic block as shown in Figure 10. This clustering enables to link discrete events of the use case specific scenario into a

Figure 10: Logistic Pipeline

Upon closer examination of the paper reels specific logistic pipeline, essential documents and logistic details need to be prepared for a proper planning orchestration prior to the ship's arrival. These documents primarily consist of the stowing plan, packing list, and the ship arrival schedule. Afterwards, daily arrivals and departures planning is organized by timeslots alongside with the required workforce, assets, and resources for each process. Currently, these event-scheduling and resource allocation processes are conformed based on expertise knowledge considering factors such as processes time estimation according to load, berth occupancy, available machinery, work in progress (WIP), weather, previous events inference, and other critical aspects.

Once the ship is docked and before proceeding with the unloading, visual inspections are carried out by an operator to identify major packing list discrepancies and possible damages to the cargo or packaging, such as water filtrations and rips. In case the quality inspection is satisfactorily passed, it is proceeded with the paper reels unloading from the ship, which are stacked on top of a Ro-Ro trailer. This process is executed by the allocated stevedores, who drive a Ro-Ro truck across the ship and couple the loaded trailer to the truck and finally drive them to the fast-unloading zone where the loaded trailers are temporary set apart.

Afterwards, trailers are transferred from the fast-unloading zone to the warehouse facilities where the procedures to store the paper reels in their definitive location begin. The warehouse pre-requirements consist of a set of procedures that ensure the successful control and management of the cargo. Firstly, the paper reels are submitted to an exhaustive identification and quality inspection control. As in the preliminary inspection conducted on the ship, this is also performed manually but under stricter standards. Meanwhile, an operator is responsible of verifying the availability of enough space to store the newly arrived cargo, in

case of necessity the warehouse space distribution is conditioned to optimally store the paper reels. Finally, clamp forklifts are handled to move the reels from the trailer to the designated area. This process typically requires a considerable number of forklifts and operators to reduce the time the trailer is not available and occupying critical warehouse manoeuvring space, hence coordination is especially relevant. All these processes are digitally registered and integrated on the warehouse management system to keep track of all the steps and ensure inventory control.

Upon retrieval request, the corresponding dispatching phase involves preparing and moving outbound cargo from the warehouse to the loading zone for final transport. This phase includes consolidating and organizing cargo based on transport schedules, verifying cargo readiness, and coordinating the necessary equipment and resources to efficiently load the cargo onto the outbound vessel or transport vehicle. Accurate documentation and inventory checks are performed to ensure that the correct cargo is dispatched, minimizing delays and maintaining a smooth flow of operations for departure.

Thus far paper reels logistic chronological lifecycle has been defined. However, processes involving different cargo types may often overlap within the same time frame, creating challenges related to coordination, resource allocation, and capacity. Regarding the exposed scenario, these processes overlap mainly occur during the paper reels unloading and the loading of general cargo dispatch, both operations are carried out in the same vessel. As illustrated in Fig. X, the use case core is focused on a specific workflow framework which consists of the automation of paper reels reception and warehousing, whereas considering the shared time-lapse with general cargo Ro-Ro loading on the same ship as a key factor of the simulation.

6.2.5.2 Proposed Operational Model

The proposed operational model for the automated version of the scenario focuses on coping with the identified user needs through the automation of processes and elements that may successfully overcome these needs.

The automated version of the paper reel unloading and loading processes, which are currently performed sequentially, will be executed simultaneously. In order to accomplish this achievement, the automation proposal will focus on replacing the truck heads driven by stevedores by autonomous guided vehicles capable of securely navigate inside the ship and coordinate. This AGV fleet will be equipped with advance navigation system, GNSS, cameras, LiDAR- based SLAM to provide the unmanned vehicle with environment-adaptive pathfinding. To achieve an unmanned navigation, the stowing plan must be digitally processed and embedded so as the ship layout distribution and the trailers' location inside the ship is provided to the vehicle. Relative to the automation of mechanics, the integration of an automated coupling system will enable the AGV to automatically hook to the loaded trailer.

The presence of STS cameras in the vicinity of the dock allows to automate the verification of the cargo with the packing list and accomplish the corresponding quality control. In addition, this cargo inspection process is currently done twice, firstly a quick check at the yard and then a thorough re-identification of the cargo prior to storage. Hence, the benefits extracted from this automation proposal is promising for enhancing the cargo inspection and monitoring of the elements.

In addition, the fleet of AGVs responsible for unloading the trailers is also in charge of transporting them autonomously to the designated area at the warehouse. At this point the automation proposal focuses on reducing the dependence on human workforce in warehouse operations to consequently increase safety and synchronization. To achieve this milestone, it becomes crucial to automate the storage and retrieval system because this processes impact directly on the overall efficiency performance of the warehouse operations. The AS/RS systems are a computer-controlled pallet racking systems designed to automatically place and retrieve materials or products from defined storage locations and encompass a wide range of technologies. Furthermore, the shunting operations that coordinate and supply the ASRS system will be executed by automated lifting vehicles (ALV), automated guided vehicles (AGV), and robotic arms. The automation of these manoeuvres ensures not only the efficient use of storage space but also the rapid and accurate location of specific reels when needed, significantly reducing the time spent in manual searching or repositioning.

The implementation of these technologies alongside event scheduling and dynamic decision support also allows maximizing the use of automated vehicles in reception and warehousing, thus reducing bottlenecks and waiting times in the workflow.

6.2.5.3 Data Flows and Interactions

The following list exhibits an overview of the data requirements for the use case:

- Paper Reels Specifications:
 - Dimensions and weight
 - Identification Number
 - Positioning Data
- Historical TOS data:
 - Material Flow
 - Storage Capacity
 - Stock histogram data
- High-precision and updated layouts: yard, warehouse, and internal roads.
- GIS Data
- Arrivals/Departures (Dates, Cargo, Operation type, and Documentation).
- List of operator categories and associated tasks.
- List of machinery with specifications:
 - Type of machine and available fleet
 - Dimensions
 - Speed
 - Paper Reels transportation capacity
 - Number of required operators for the usage of each machinery

- Planning.
- Idle and Waiting times.
- Process execution time measures.
- The KPI definitions and formulas.

The previous classification showcases the required data types clustered by their intrinsic nature and provenance. However, to gain a deeper understanding of the interactions among various data types, it is essential to previously understand the application and functionality beyond the purpose to which they comply with.

Building on this classification, the integration of data from various sources is necessary to create a realistic physical model of the port terminal for simulation environment. The foundation of this model relies on the combination of high-precision and updated layouts of the areas of interest and GIS data. This integration enables to distribute port terminal areas based on purpose, requirements and specifications, internal road mapping, accurate dimensionality, spatial relations and functionalities between terminal zones, and spatial distribution of critical areas, such as the warehouse.

Figure 11: Simulation environment

Additionally, monitoring data primarily is related to cargo and port terminal equipment which ideally is extracted by IoT sensors connected to a database. The essential data that must be considered from these assets consists of three data types:

ID: enables to individually identify each element.

Position: precisely identify the location of each element.

Status: consist of various discrete states.

Paper Reels: received, quality control, in transport, waiting, and stored.

Equipment: free, on duty, in transit and maintenance.

Figure 12: Generic lifecycle of data flows and interactions

The flowchart (Figure 13: Data flow Chart) showcases the generic lifecycle of data flows and interactions among different data sources, specifications, and applications. The presence of feedback loops enables predictive algorithms to learn from historical events and performances, thus improving planning accuracy and adaptability of asset allocation to unexpected circumstances.

The data flowchart applies to a fixed time-lapse. Suppose a daily time slot window, in which the port authorities receive the vessel arrival/departure schedule. This information is the input to internal algorithms that generate an optimal planning of event-scheduling for each process and asset allocation based on historical and monitoring data. Afterwards, operational and idle times of each process are measured. Based on the compiled data and the estimated impact on future planning operations, the monitoring data is fed back to the system for planning and resource allocation adjustment.

Figure 13: Data flow Chart

6.3 UC3 : Automated shunting as a Service oriented platform

6.3.1 Use Case definition

6.3.1.1 Purpose and Scope

The purpose of this use case is to explore and evaluate the implementation of autonomous technologies in MIS terminal, an inland terminal dedicated to intermodal freight.

The scope includes simulating the terminal's anticipated layout and operations to assess the potential impact of automation in handling the expected traffic. This approach replicates the terminal's current and future configurations and provide a comprehensive representation of anticipated operations. By simulating the current operations, it allows to understand the impact of automation on a small and complex reality. By incorporating potential operating procedures that have not been implemented, it enables an exploration of how automation may enhance the terminal's efficiency, adaptability, and overall capability to meet evolving demands. Furthermore, simulating the automation allows to introduce the optimization of features that are inherently connected with autonomous solutions.

6.3.1.2 General Overview of the Use Case

UC3 aims to evaluate and advance the implementation of automation in intermodal freight transport, focusing on optimizing current and future operational flows at the MIS terminal. The terminal under consideration has a complex and constraining layout. However, it is currently undergoing expansion and,

within 10 years, will feature significantly larger infrastructure and increased capacity. Studying the introduction of automation using simulations for both the current and future terminal setups allows for a detailed comparison of its effectiveness in different scenarios, highlighting potential benefits and challenges.

Autonomous equipment, a cornerstone of automation, requires continuous input to operate efficiently. As such, planning autonomous operations must prioritize the smart and efficient use of this equipment to maximize performance. By simulating these operations, critical factors that influence efficiency can be identified and addressed early, ensuring the terminal is well-prepared for future demands.

Notably, many roles and equipment required in the future are not yet in place, presenting an opportunity to avoid some common setbacks associated with automation. This can be achieved by investing directly in the appropriate equipment, personnel training, and developing best practices, while designing process flows from the ground up.

Although the terminal operates within an intermodal system, this case focuses primarily on the organization and movement of rail freight. The operations are directed toward the efficient arrangement of train operations. A more efficient rail process would allow the terminal to switch part of its road transport to a multimodal train-road solution. This approach optimizes cargo flow within terminals and ensures that trains are prepared for their next destination or for loading/unloading in the intermodal environment while remaining a competitive element in the supply chain even in circumstances where the infrastructural conditions are not favourable.

6.3.2 State-of-the-Art analysis of automated shunting trains operations

Shunting, also known as yard operations, is the process of moving railway wagons from one track to another. In the AutoMoTIF project the focus is on movement of trains between different tracks of local logistic nodes, such as stations and inland rail terminal. These operations are usually carried out by dedicated personnel and not by the Railway Undertaking.

This process plays a crucial role in the overall impact of freight train operations, both in terms of human and material resources. Smooth shunting facilitates and improves the organization of other train related operations, for instance allowing for a better management of cargo loading and unloading procedures.

In the context of intermodal operations and focusing the narrative to the Use Case, shunting operations ensure that the trains are correctly assembled, disassembled, and positioned. Shunting train operations involve several tasks that will be defined in this document. Some of these are:

- Coupling and uncoupling railcars
- Repositioning locomotives
- Coordinating the movement of rail vehicles

All these operations are very relevant for the intermodal transport, where cargo is moved between different types of vehicles or modes of transportation (rail, road, and waterways). In these scenarios, if the shunting process is truly efficient, it contributes significantly to reducing delays, enhancing safety, and improving the overall productivity.

Traditionally, shunting operations have been 100% manual labour, with human operators controlling all the activities, locomotives and coordinating the movements of railcars. However, as the necessity of increase the efficiency and reliability in freight transport appears, the need of automate in shunting has become more evident. For this, advances technologies are needed, for example, remote-controlled locomotives, automated guided vehicles (AGVs), and intelligent traffic management systems. Later in this document, this technologies will be listed and defined.

The integration of automation in shunting not only enhances operational efficiency but also reduces the potential for human error, improving also the safety in rail environments. Rail operators and logistics providers are trying to modernize their infrastructure and processes, so the adoption of automated shunting technologies represents a crucial step in order to optimize the supply chain and meet the demands of contemporary freight transport.

Figure 14: Shunting Process Phases diagram

Here below a breakdown of the shunting process is presented, separating all the process into different key phases:

Phase	Description
Pre-arrival and entry	<p>Process to handle wagons starts before the train enters the facility. The exchange of information between the infrastructure manager (IM) and the yard operator is the first step. This information comprises the expected time of arrival (ETA), train composition, the type of cargo or the next destination.</p> <p>Before the home signal displays "proceed" and allows the train to access the facility, the yard must allocate a track in the arrival yard. Additionally, a secured route to the designated track must be established.</p>
Arrival of the Train	<p>This phase begins with the arrival of a train at the terminal or yard. Upon arrival, the train is typically stationary and prepared for further operations. Notifications regarding the train's arrival are communicated to the shunting crew and terminal management to organize full wagons within the yard for efficient intermodal transfers.</p>

<p>Assessment and Planning</p>	<p>Once the train has arrived, an assessment is conducted to determine the required shunting operations. This includes analysing the composition of the train (including the inspection of the wagons for possible damages, the comparison of the received wagons with the documentation and removing of the end-of-train signal), identifying which wagons need to be moved and where, and determining the optimal track for unloading or reconfiguration. This phase often involves collaboration between dispatchers and shunting operators to devise an efficient plan.</p>
<p>Execution of Shunting Operations</p>	<p>This is the phase where shunting operations takes places. This phase includes several key activities:</p> <p>Coupling and Uncoupling: Operators or automated systems will couple or uncouple railcars, ensuring the correct configuration for the next leg of the journey or unloading. It is important to mention here, that several initiatives and project are currently on going, in order to automate all this processes, like the initiative named “Europe’s Rail Digital Automated Coupling”.</p> <p>Repositioning of Locomotives: Mainline locomotive is typically moved away and a shunting locomotive will approach to start the reposition or any other internal movements of the wagons in the yard.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moving away mainline locomotive: this includes the draining of the brake pipe, after that the staff uncouple the locomotive and disconnect the brake pipe, and finally the locomotive receives a route to a different track or to the next shunting operations. • Approach of shunting locomotive: this includes the coupling of the wagons to the shunting locomotive <p>Movement of Railcars: The assigned shunting locomotive will then move the railcars to their designated tracks according to the shunting plan. This movement can involve intricate manoeuvres, particularly in busy terminals.</p>
<p>Completion of Shunting Tasks</p>	<p>Once all planned movements are completed (the shunting is done), the technology system used in this phase verifies that the railcars are correctly positioned, and all tasks have been executed according to the shunting plan. This verification includes checking for any issues that may have arisen during the process and activate the break of wagons if needed.</p>
<p>Departure of Railcars</p>	<p>After the successful completion of the shunting tasks and the check of them, the railcars are prepared for their next journey. It can be loading onto another train, being transported by truck, or moving to a storage area.</p> <p>The preparation process (before the train departs) begins with the manual coupling of the mainline locomotive to the wagons and the manual connection of the brake pipe. This is followed by the train’s brake calculation, a comprehensive brake test, and a check of the wagon order, alongside a detailed inspection of the</p>

	<p>wagons. Before receiving clearance from the signalling system to depart the yard, the end-of-train device must also be installed.</p> <p>Two new processes stand out due to their time-consuming nature: the thorough inspection of the train and wagons, and the comprehensive brake test.</p>
Transversal phases	Description
Resource Allocation	Starting with the allocation of the track at the very beginning until giving the green light to the departure of the train, the resource allocation is present. This may include deploying locomotives, assigning operators, preparing the wagons, etc that will assist during all the process. Proper resource allocation is critical to ensure that operations proceed smoothly and efficiently.
Monitoring and Adjustments	During all the process of the shunting operations, real-time monitoring is continuously used to ensure safety and operational efficiency. Supervisors or automated systems continuously assess all the process, for example, the movement of railcars, adjusting as necessary to accommodate any unexpected changes or delays in the operation.
Additional phases	Description
Data analysis and Reporting	Post-operation, data from the shunting process is collected and analysed. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as turnaround times, resource utilization, and efficiency are evaluated. This analysis helps identify areas for improvement and informs future shunting operations.
Feedback Loop	Insights gained from data analysis feed back into the operational processes, allowing for continuous refinement of shunting strategies and practices. This phase fosters a culture of improvement, ensuring that operations become increasingly efficient over time.

Table 17: Shunting train operations Phases

6.3.2.1 Current Technology state

In this section, a comprehensive analysis of the current technology state in the shunting operations has been done, and concretely, regarding the intermodal terminals (focusing on train operations).

In the table below, an exploration of the various technologies currently employed in shunting operations is included, from automated control systems to remote-controlled locomotives, and for each of them a description and the nowadays current applications is made. The objective of mapping out these technologies together is to provide a clear understanding of how automation is transforming the shunting processes.

Pre-arrival and entry of the train + Arrival of the train	
Intelligent video gate (IVG)	<u>Description:</u> Intelligent Video Gate (IVG) systems use advanced camera technologies combined with AI-driven image recognition to automatically scan and record train and which type of cargo transports as the train pass

	<p>through specific entry points. These systems offer real-time data on train composition, cargo condition, and other relevant metrics.</p> <p><u>Current Applications:</u> Different types of IVG technology are already in use in rail freight terminals and intermodal operations. For example, in Europe and Asia, this type of systems is used in ports and rail terminals facilitating the automated cargo inspection, increasing up the entry processes and reducing human intervention. The implementations of this type of systems often include automatic number plate recognition (ANPR) and optical character recognition (OCR) for container and wagon tracking.</p>
Assessment and Planning	
Shunting Control Software	<p><u>Description:</u> This software analyses the incoming train's configuration and determines the most efficient shunting plan based on operational data and historical performance.</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Used in terminals to assist and assess dispatchers in order to create the most optimal shunting strategy.</p>
Traffic Management Systems (TMS)	<p><u>Description:</u> TMS integrates various data sources to manage and optimize rail traffic flow, ensuring efficient use of tracks and minimizing delays</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Employed in busy rail networks to coordinate multiple trains, prevent congestion, and enhance scheduling accuracy.</p>
Execution of Shunting Operation	
Remote-Controlled Locomotives	<p><u>Description:</u> Remote-controlled locomotives enhance safety by reducing the need for operators to be physically present in high-risk areas, such as between railcars during coupling and uncoupling operations. Allowing the operators to manage locomotive movements from distance, the risk of injuries is minimized to practically zero, particularly in confined or busy terminal environments. Additionally, another advantage of this technology is that a remote operation can provide better visibility and control.</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Day by day the use of this locomotives is increasing in terminals to facilitate and improve the shunting operations. The last stage of remote-controlled locomotives, in combination with Automated Train Operations (ATO) system, is fully autonomous locomotives. Autonomous locomotives are reaching increasing Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) (source: Alstom).</p>
Mobile Robots	<p><u>Description:</u> Mobile robots are autonomous systems designed to navigate terminal environments and perform auxiliary tasks (for example the transport of tools, equipment, small components, etc.). These robots operate through predefined paths, without interfering with main rail operations (Vega&Reyes, 2022).</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Employed in several intermodal terminals to automate the movement of several components, reducing manual labour and increasing efficiency.</p>
Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)	<p><u>Description:</u> AGVs are “mobile robots” that use predefined paths to transport railcars within the terminal totally autonomously. Usually, these vehicles are used to autonomously transport full rail wagons within the terminals, optimizing the movement of freight wagons rather than individual cargo units.</p>

	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Starting to be used in several intermodal terminals to automate the movement of railcars, reducing manual labour and increasing efficiency.</p>
Automated Coupling Systems	<p><u>Description:</u> These systems automate the coupling and uncoupling of railcars, reducing the need for manual intervention during the operations.</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Shunting locomotives are very often equipped with automated or semiautomated coupling systems, leading to more efficient operations.</p>
Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC)	<p><u>Description:</u> Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC) is an advanced Automated Coupling System that automates the process of coupling and uncoupling wagons. The technology connects wagons mechanically, electrically, and digitally. DAC also supports real-time data and power transmission across wagons, making rail freight operations more efficient and better suited for modern digital systems (RSSB, 2020). DAC is a key element for the automation of rail freight enabling automated brake testing, ATO, and the implementation of Train Integrity Monitoring System (TIMS)</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> DAC is being tested in Europe, particularly and mostly in Germany and Switzerland, as part of efforts to modernize rail freight. The technology is used to speed up train assembly, enhance safety by reducing manual labour, and allow real-time monitoring of wagon conditions.</p>
Self-propelled freight wagon	<p><u>Description:</u> Self-propelled freight wagons are equipped with embedded motors and power systems, allowing them to move independently without the need for a locomotive pushing them.</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> This technology is still in the early stages of development, with a very low Technology Readiness Level (TRL). Current prototypes are being tested in controlled environments to evaluate feasibility and performance in reducing delays and increasing efficiency in yard operations.</p>
Intelligent freight wagons	<p><u>Description:</u> Intelligent freight wagons integrate IoT sensors and digital communication modules to monitor and transmit real-time data about the wagon's condition, load status, and environmental factors (Luo, et al. 2021).</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Intelligent freight wagons are being piloted in advanced rail systems in Europe, Asia and North America. These systems enable predictive maintenance by detecting issues such as wheel wear or temperature anomalies, and they provide cargo monitoring for sensitive goods. Current implementations include collaborations with rail freight operators to create smarter and more connected supply chains.</p>
Completion of Shunting Tasks	
Task Verification Systems	<p><u>Description:</u> Systems that confirm automatically the completion of shunting tasks and ensure that railcars are correctly positioned according to the operational plan for the next railcars destinations.</p>
	<p><u>Current Applications:</u> Is used currently in terminals to validate that all operations have been completed as the requirements indicates, enhancing accountability and accuracy.</p>
Automated Reporting Tools	<p><u>Description:</u> Software's that automatically generates reports on shunting operations, including performance metrics and task completion statuses.</p>

	<u>Current Applications:</u> Implemented in terminals to speed up the reporting processes and facilitate data analysis.
Departure of Railcars	
Departure Management Systems	<u>Description:</u> These systems manage the scheduling and the departure of railcars, ensuring they leave the terminal on time and in the best possible way.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used in intermodal terminals to coordinate departures and improve the overall efficiency of the rail logistic section.
Integrated Communication Systems	<u>Description:</u> Technologies that facilitate communication between different systems, infrastructures and personnel involved in all the shunting process, in order to have a perfect coordination.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Employed to enhance collaboration among operators, dispatchers, and other stakeholders in the today's terminals.
Resource Allocation	
Locomotive Management Systems	<u>Description:</u> These systems track the availability and the status of locomotives, facilitating effective allocation based on current operational requirements.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Is currently used by rail operators to maximize the utilization of locomotives and ensure that the right and most possible resources are available.
Automated Resource / Allocation Tools	<u>Description:</u> These tools use algorithms to allocate personnel and equipment for shunting operations based on real-time data.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Implemented in terminals to improve the efficiency of resource deployment and reduce operational problems and delays.
Monitoring and Adjustments	
Real-Time Monitoring Systems	<u>Description:</u> Systems equipped with sensors and cameras that continuously monitor the conditions of railcars and locomotives, providing live feedback about them to the operators.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Is used in the most part of terminals in order to ensure safety and upscaling the operational efficiency by allowing immediate response to any issues.
Predictive Analytic Tools	<u>Description:</u> These tools analyse historical and real-time data to prevent and simulate potential disruptions, problems or equipment failures, allowing proactive adjustments in order to solve problems before them appears.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Integrated into shunting operations to improve reliability and minimize delays by predicting maintenance needs.
Additional Phases	
Automation of brake test	<u>Description:</u> Automated brake testing systems eliminate the need for manual inspection by using sensors and digital controls to test brake performance remotely.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> While these technologies are still in the adoption and earlier stages, automated brake test systems are being trailed in rail yards specially in Europe and North America. These trials aim to validate the technology's reliability and efficiency compared to manual testing methods. Initial results show promise in reducing delays during pre-departure checks and improving safety compliance. (Sánchez Martín, 2019)

Feedback Management Systems	Description: Platforms that collect insights and performance data from shunting operations to inform future improvements and operational strategies.
	Current Applications: Implemented in rail operations to foster a culture of continuous improvement, allowing for the adaptation of processes based on real-time feedback.

Table 18: Shunting phases technologies

6.3.2.2 Case Studies

In this next section, we will explore two specific real cases to show the implementation of automated shunting operations and technologies in real intermodal terminals.

The examples will highlight, and remark practical applications of the technologies listed and defined earlier in the document.

→ Case Study 1: Port of Trieste

Description of the terminal: The Port of Trieste is located in Europe, specifically at the crossroads of important shipping routes and the Baltic-Adriatic and Mediterranean TEN-T core network corridors. Is considered an international hub, so it is used as an important gateway for overland and maritime trade, particularly with Central and Eastern Europe. The port process approximately 8,000 trains annually, with around 25% operating within a conventional horizontal marshalling system. The rail services connect this port with several destinations around Austria, Germany, Hungary, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Switzerland, while national services link to Milan Certosa, Padua, and Bologna.

Figure 15: Port of Trieste

The rail infrastructure at the port is complex, with shunting operations split between two main sites: Campo Marzio and Servola. The marshalling yard, located at the southern end of the Baltic-Adriatic corridor, plays a key role in the port's operations, used for frequent rail connections to Austria, including 80 trains per week.

Overview of the case study: The case study at the Port of Trieste focuses on the optimization of its rail activities and shunting operations, which were restructured in 2016 and upgraded in the following years. The operator ADRIAFER, a subsidiary of the Port of Trieste Authority, owns last-mile operations in the region. Due to the train length limitations of 550 meters, the infrastructure was currently undergoing upgrades to accommodate 750-meter trains, improving overall operational capacity.

One of the primary challenges identified in this case study was the limited space and the complex layout of the port's rail network. To address this problem, this case study examined the potential of the infrastructure for optimize the medium-sized marshalling yard using simulation models (the same point of AutoMoTIF project). Since the port's high level of activity made it difficult to test optimizations on live traffic, a simulation model of the Trieste yard was developed by Simcon, providing a virtual environmental simulation to assess various optimization strategies.

The simulation model for the Trieste rail terminal was developed through a collaborative effort, involving not only SIMCON but also the VILLON and OPENTRACK simulation tools as part of the OPTIYARD project). This multi-tool approach allowed and provided a comprehensive analysis of the marshalling yard, combining the strengths of each simulation platform to optimize rail operations. The OPTIYARD project leveraged these technologies to explore various optimization strategies without stopping the live operations.

Technologies used: For achieving the goals, the Port of Trieste incorporated several key technologies to improve its rail and shunting operations. The infrastructure is being upgraded since 2016 to include six tracks of 750 meters, addressing current train length limitations problem. The port is also investing in 12 autonomous locomotives and two Zephyr railroad engines to boost efficiency and improve the use of existing tracks. Additionally, communication systems with the Italian infrastructure manager Rete Ferroviaria Italiana (RFI) have been also upgraded to monitor trains two hours prior to their arrival at the yards, enabling more efficient coordination and scheduling.

While automation of marshalling operations is still under analysis and development, the use of simulation technology was crucial to give the port all the elements and tools for exploring the potential improvements. The simulation model offered a detailed description of the marshalling yard areas and the rail network, providing all the insights for the testing of optimization strategies without impacting real-world operations.

Results: When the case study was finished, it demonstrated the potential benefits of automating the rail and shunting operations, but also remarked the difficulty of implementing this improvement into the high intense activity port environment (also a relevant barrier for our project partners). The simulation model provided valuable insights into how the layout and track utilization could be improved in the context of automation under different scenarios; and the detailed network and yard models helped identify bottleneck and problems, and proposed solutions that could improve overall operational efficiency once implemented.

The ongoing upgrades to the rail infrastructure, the introduction of new locomotives and the improvement of the communication systems, significantly improved the port's operational capacity regarding the shunting activities. Additionally, the analysis highlighted the importance of further automating marshalling operations to fully optimize the yard's performance, a direction the port is currently exploring for future advancements.

→ Case Study 2: "RANG-E" Project: Autonomous shunting on the port railway

Project goal: The Rang-E project explored the possibilities and challenges of the implementation of smarter train traffic management tools on the railways of the port of Bremerhaven.

The project aimed to address the human involvement in shunting operations (and also improving the automation of them) and the interference of crossing traffic handling equipment. A key aspect to approach the pilot to autonomous shunting.

Description of the terminal (Bremerhaven): The Port of Bremerhaven is a key hub for maritime logistics in Germany. Is specialized on containers and automobile handling. As one of Europe’s largest terminals, it plays a crucial role in the region’s traffic, and the rail transport part is an important aspect of this port.

The port handles millions of TEUs (twenty-foot equivalent units) of cargo annually and is known for its advanced logistics infrastructure, supporting a high volume of ship calls and efficient multimodal connectivity.

Solution approach: Rang-E serves as a feasibility study to evaluate the potential for autonomous shunting operations on the Bremerhaven port railway; examining technical, economic, and legal factors.

By automating shunting operations, the main goal was to optimize the scheduling and management of locomotives of the port, for containers and automobile charges. The project assessed different types of automation (or levels), starting from partial automation in specific tasks to fully autonomous and self-directed shunting locomotives and operations.

Additionally, the study explored the viability of power the shunting operations by electric accumulators reducing the diesel consume (also interesting for AutoMoTIF regarding the sustainability aspects). The port also included in the context of this project digitalization tools, like Internet of Things (IoT) and Logistics 4.0 for the port operator.

Results: The outcomes of the Rang-E feasibility study highlighted and listed the potential and challenges of introducing intelligent train traffic control in port railways.

A comprehensive needs assessment was conducted, identifying the weaknesses and the legal aspects issues in the current system. Like in the AutoMoTIF project, different scenarios were defined, and technical, legal, and organizational aspects were analysed. Using interviews with experts, port workers, port railway authorities, shunting service providers and other stakeholders, a process model (based on BPMN 2.0) was developed.

The analysis found difficulties and barriers in areas like processes (manual operated switches, coupling and uncoupling locomotives and wagons, etc), infrastructures, the adoption of the new technologies and the process of communication. A key finding was that the efforts toward automation must be focused to immediate cost-saving opportunities (efficiencies, reducing equipment use, reduce the personal costs, etc.). The simulation supports and confirm this points but also identified some areas that requires further research to advances the implementation of autonomous shunting operations.

→ **Others**

Port	Description of the case study
DB Cargo (Germany)	Overview: DB Cargo, which is the largest rail freight operator in Germany, has initiated and developed different projects to improve its shunting operations using the automation.

	<p>Technologies Used: Remote-controlled locomotives and automated shunting systems.</p> <p>Results: These innovations have improved operational efficiency and safety in the port, with a significant reduction in manual handling and the improvement for faster service times.</p>
ProRail (Netherlands)	<p>Overview: ProRail, responsible for managing the railway infrastructure in the Netherlands, is exploring automated shunting solutions to modernize rail operations with various projects implemented in the port.</p> <p>Technologies Used: Automated locomotives and advanced traffic management systems.</p> <p>Results: Early results remarks the improvement of the efficiency in managing rail traffic and highlighted the importance of coordination between different transport models.</p>
Kuehne + Nagel (Switzerland)	<p>Overview: Kuehne + Nagel (which is a leading global logistics company) is integrating automated shunting processes into its operations at selected rail terminals.</p> <p>Technologies Used: The use of AGVs and automated coupling systems is being piloted to enhance coordination between rail and road transport.</p> <p>Results: Initial implementations have shown promise in reducing delays and improving the overall efficiency of logistics operations.</p>
Europe's Rail JU project FP1 MOTIONAL	<p>Overview/objective: digitalisation of the rail system.</p> <p>Technologies researched:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Management and Mobility Integration: Development of flexible, efficient, and resilient European rail network management strategies, including integration with other transport modes for seamless mobility. • Digital Twin Environment: Implementation of a Digital Twin environment to simulate and optimize rail operations and asset management, enhancing decision-making processes. <p>Results: the project will finish by September 2026</p>
Europe's Rail JU project FP2 R2DATO	<p>Overview/objective: increasing automation of the rail systems</p> <p>Technologies researched:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automated Train Operations (ATO): Research and development of scalable automation in train operations, including GoA3/4 automation levels, to optimize operations and increase network capacity. • Technical Enablers: Demonstration of technical enablers such as hybrid level three, moving block, and Train Integrity Monitoring System (TIMS), which are crucial for advanced automation

	Results: the project will finish by September 2026 but first tangible results expected to be delivered by 2025
Europe's Rail JU project FP5 TRANS4M-R	<p>Overview: advancing rail freight transport</p> <p>Technologies researched:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Automatic Coupler (DAC): Development and testing of the Digital Automatic Coupler to enhance efficiency in freight operations. • Green Freight Services: Implementation of sustainable and competitive digital green rail freight services, aligning with environmental objectives. <p>Results: the project will finish by March 2026</p>

Table 19: Use Case 3, Case Studies

6.3.3 User needs and technological gaps

This section will delve into the specific user needs associated with shunting operations, as well as the technological gaps that must be bridged to enhance overall performance and drive progress in the rail logistics sector.

The section has been constructed with the feedback and the insights of the project partners implicated in this Use Case and external experts. The following key user needs have been identified:

User need	Information
Operational needs	
Fast and Reliable Automated Coupling/Decoupling Systems	<p>Description: Operators require automated systems that can quickly and accurately couple and decouple wagons to maintain a fast flow of shunting operations; with the objective of minimize times and delays during these processes.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Implement robust and efficient coupling/decoupling technologies, such as Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC) technologies, that can operate reliably under high demand, reducing time and minimizing manual intervention.</p>
Precision in Wagon Positioning for Sequential Shunting Tasks	<p>Description: Being precise with the relocation of wagons is essential to get sequential shunting tasks and avoid potential necessary manual adjustments (which will be very inefficient), especially in busy yards with frequent reconfigurations.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Adopt automated guidance systems and precise positioning technologies (e.g., GPS, laser guidance) ensuring that each wagon is perfectly aligned for the next sequence.</p>

<p>Reduction of Wagon Coupling and Decoupling Time</p>	<p>Description: One of the points that will encourage the ports to automate the shunting operations, is to reduce the time spent on coupling/decoupling to increase the efficiency and avoid bottlenecks.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Integrate high-speed automated coupling systems that can handle multiple operations simultaneously, reducing waiting times and enabling higher throughput during shunting.</p>
<p>Energy Optimization During Automated Shunting Movements</p>	<p>Description: Energy-efficient shunting is essential in order to reduce operational costs and environmental impact (González-Gil, et al. 2014).</p> <p>Need for solutions: Deploy energy management systems that optimize power use during each phase of shunting, including acceleration, deceleration, and idle times.</p>
<p>Automation of routinary tasks</p>	<p>Description: Shunting is governed by a strict set of rules regulating routine tasks that are performed manually. These tasks are often time- and resource-consuming, such as the braking test or the wagon inspection.</p> <p>Need for solution: the full or partial automation of these tasks would significantly improve the performance of terminals</p>
<p>Management needs</p>	
<p>Efficient Track Allocation for High-Volume Shunting</p>	<p>Description: Shunting yards need an efficient allocation system to manage track space dynamically, ensuring optimal use of available tracks and reducing congestion.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Implement real-time track management systems that allocate tracks based on current and anticipated demand, balancing track utilization to avoid overloading certain areas.</p>
<p>Optimized Resource Allocation</p>	<p>Description: Optimal distribution of locomotives and operators is essential to minimize delays and maximize the efficiency of shunting operations.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Use AI-driven resource management tools to allocate personnel, locomotives, and equipment based on real-time data.</p>
<p>Real-Time Operational Overview</p>	<p>Description: Operators require a centralized, real-time view of shunting operations to monitor progress and quickly respond to issues, ensuring coordinated and efficient workflows.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Develop a centralized control platform that aggregates data from all operational stages, providing live updates on wagon status, track availability, and resource usage, enabling proactive adjustments.</p>
<p>Compliance with Automated Safety Standards</p>	<p>Description: Automation must meet strict safety standards to protect personnel and equipment, particularly in areas with high volumes of movement and complex operations.</p>

	Need for solutions: Implement automated safety monitoring systems with emergency stops, proximity sensors, and adherence to regulatory standards.
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Table 20: User Needs, Use Case 3

While significant advancements have been made in shunting technologies, various gaps still exist that hinder the full optimization of shunting operations within intermodal terminals. The following **key gaps** have been identified:

Key gap	Information
Automation Limitations	<p>Description: Despite the introduction of automated solutions, many shunting operations still are done using manual labor. Current automation technologies often operate in isolation, lacking the capability for full autonomy in executing complex shunting tasks.</p> <p>Impact: This limitation results in inefficiencies and an increased risk of human error during operations, hindering the overall productivity of shunting processes.</p>
Interoperability Issues	<p>Description: Many terminals use a mix of legacy and modern systems, leading to challenges in integrating new technologies with existing infrastructure. Interoperability between different automation solutions and manual processes is often a problem.</p> <p>Impact: These integration challenges can create operational issues, reduce data sharing capabilities, and complicate coordination efforts among different systems.</p>
Data utilization challenges	<p>Description: While data is increasingly collected from various sources, the lack of advanced analytics and reporting tools limits users' ability to really use and take profit of this information for the process of decision-making.</p> <p>Impact: Not good data utilization can result in missed opportunities for optimizing operations, and also the appearance of inefficiencies and slower response times to operational issues.</p>
Maintenance and Support Shortcomings	<p>Description: The maintenance of automated systems can be complex and expensive, and many organizations are in trouble to find personnel with the necessary skills to manage and maintain these technologies effectively.</p> <p>Impact: Insufficient maintenance can lead to increased downtime, reduced reliability, and higher operational costs. Predictive maintenance should be a good solution (Ntalampiras & Spiros, 2022).</p>
Scalability Concerns	<p>Description: Current shunting technologies may not scale effectively to improve in the future for increase the cargo volume or changes in operational demands.</p> <p>Impact: This lack of scalability can result in bottlenecks during peak periods, reducing the terminal's ability to meet growing market demands, and making the ports to prefer the manual labors in front of the automated ones.</p>

<p>Limited Predictive Capabilities</p>	<p>Description: While some predictive analytics tools exist, the affordable one capabilities are often limited, and they may not provide comprehensive insights into all aspects of shunting operations.</p> <p>Impact: Inadequate predictive capabilities can lead to unanticipated disruptions, increased maintenance needs, and a lack of preparedness for operational challenges.</p>
<p>Insufficient User Training Resources</p>	<p>Description: As new technologies are adopted, there is often a gap in training programs that adequately prepare personnel to operate these systems effectively. Many organizations do not have comprehensive training materials or resources. We have to include here the retisences of the personnel to this changes.</p> <p>Impact: This gap can result in operators angry and also not fully understanding how to utilize new technologies.</p>

Table 21: Technological GAPS, Use Case 3

6.3.4 Use Case Scenarios

6.3.4.1 Scenario 1: Current train-related operations in inland terminal

Narrative Description

The scenario centres on train operations within a multimodal inland terminal, encompassing all rail-related activities from the arrival of trains at the arrival station to their actual departure.

Specifically, trains arrive at a large rail station located at a significant distance from the terminal, requiring shunting operations to transfer railcars into the terminal. These shunting activities are particularly complex due to their reliance on the national railway network and existing infrastructural constraints. Additionally, internal shunting manoeuvres within the terminal are necessary to allow proper loading operations. Once the train's service is complete, it is returned to the station.

To manage the high costs associated with shunting, empty locomotive trips are minimized. Consequently, trains are introduced and extracted from the terminal in a way that ensures each trip in one direction is followed by a corresponding return trip with for a different train, necessitating efficient planning and operational management to optimize both resource utilization and overall efficiency.

Key Variables and Parameters

This section outlines the possible variables that impact the train-related operations within the terminal.

Possible Variables:

Terminal and tracks layout

Traffic dimensions: the number of trains served, and the volume of containers handled, which are directly influenced.

Traffic distribution on time: schedules of the departures and arrivals

Terminal resources:

- Equipment available for operations.

- Terminal staff

6.3.4.2 Scenario 2: Expected train-related operations in renovated inland terminal

Narrative Description

The scenario envisions train-related operations within the multimodal inland terminal, after it has undergone significant infrastructural renovations. It studies the future terminal layout and anticipated operations, encompassing the entire process from the arrival of trains at the nearby station to their departure. It covers all key activities, including loading, unloading, and the transfer of cargo throughout the terminal, ensuring a comprehensive view of the operational workflow.

Specifically, the train arrives at a nearby rail station, necessitating shunting operations to bring the railcars into the terminal. Once inside, autonomous cranes, in coordination with autonomous tugs, manage unloading and loading operations. To ensure the efficient operation of the equipment and accurately simulate these activities, dedicated models and algorithms are essential. These algorithms will optimize decision-making at both the local level and across the entire operation, maximizing efficiency and overall system performance.

Key Variables and Parameters

This section outlines the possible variables that impact the train-related operations within the terminal.

Possible Variables:

Traffic dimensions: the number of trains served and the volume of containers handled, which are directly influenced.

Traffic distribution: on time, train features (length, etc), ...

Equipment type and quantity: the diversity and number of equipment available for operations.

6.3.5 Concept of Operations (ConOps)

6.3.5.1 Current Operational Environment

Scenario 1

The current operational environment associated with shunting operations for introducing and extracting trains from the terminal involves three interconnected nodes:

Arrival and departure station. The Brescia station, positioned on the national rail network, is a large hub for both passenger and freight traffic.

Transfer station. Montirone Station, located over 10 km from the arrival and departure station and near the terminal entrance. This station serves as a vital link between the national rail network and the terminal entrance. Although primarily designed to support passenger services, the station has limited freight-handling capabilities, offering only a single short handover track. Furthermore, a section of the line leading to the station is not electrified, necessitating the use of specialized diesel-electric locomotives for transferring rail segments.

Intermodal Terminal The terminal is a multimodal rail-road terminal that facilitates the transfer of goods between rail and road transport. Its infrastructure includes two tracks with workable lengths of approximately 470 and 450 meters, alongside a yard divided into two areas by lighting towers.

Figure 16: Shunting operations environment

These infrastructure limitations and operational constraints shape the workflow and processes for introducing and extracting trains from the terminal.

Upon arrival at the Brescia station (1), trains exceeding the operational length limit must be divided into shorter segments (2). The segments are then transferred individually and sequentially to the terminal. To reach the terminal, each section is first transferred to a transfer station and then introduced in it (3,4). Due to the partial electrification of the connecting line, a specialized interoperable locomotive is used for these tasks.

Figure 17: Scenario 1 schematic shunting operations diagram

The division of the train into multiple parts (usually two) involves decoupling the locomotive from the train and moving it to position the split. After identifying the correct location for the split, the two segments are decoupled, and a diesel-electric locomotive is attached to one segment. This locomotive is then used to pull the segment to the intermediate station. Before the train reaches the intermediate station, the segment must receive clearance from the railway network's control room to safely pass a level crossing.

From the intermediate station, the section is pushed into the terminal through a manually operated gate. Ground personnel oversee the gate's operation, ensuring the train's safe entry. Once the entire train is inside the terminal, loading and unloading operations can commence.

Due to the way container unloading and loading operations are carried out, only the track closer to the container yard can be utilized at any given time. As a result, once the operations on one segment are completed (Figure 17: Scenario 1 schematic shunting operations diagram, the two segments must switch positions (Figure 18: Shunting segmentation). To achieve this, the first segment is pushed onto the entrance line using a locotractor, owned by the terminal for the movements inside the terminal. Afterward, the second segment is pushed onto the same line and immediately pulled into its desired track (7,8). The first segment is then repositioned onto the remaining track, completing the switch and allowing the loading operation to be carried out on the second segment.

Figure 18: Shunting segmentation

After the operations are complete, the train is extracted from the terminal in parts (9,10). To exit the terminal and reach the intermediate station, a locomotive must be attached to the segment and all standard operational procedures and safety verifications are carried out. The segment is then pulled through the manually operated gate and requires clearance from the railway network's control room.

At the transfer station, the locomotive is repositioned to the opposite end of the train for its return to the main rail station. Once both segments are at the departure station, they are reassembled to form a complete train (11), and the train can depart (12).

To manage shunting costs, empty locomotive trips are minimized. This approach ensures that each inbound trip is paired with a corresponding outbound trip for another train, maximizing resource utilization and operational efficiency.

Scenario 2

The scenario considers the terminal layout following the completion of planned infrastructural renovations, with significant modifications anticipated both inside and outside the terminal.

On the national railway network, the renovations will enable the station closest to the terminal to accommodate electric locomotives and receive full-length trains of 700 meters long. This development will allow it to serve as the primary arrival and departure station, drastically changing the operations.

Within the terminal, the proposed layout includes extending the two existing tracks and adding three new 450-meter tracks to increase operational capacity. Additionally, a substantial area will be allocated for a new container storage yard, further enhancing the terminal's efficiency.

Figure 19: Proposed layout

As a result, trains arrive at the closest station, where the railway operator's locomotive would decouple and depart. The rolling stock is then coupled with a terminal locomotive and seamlessly pushed into the terminal passing the manually operated gates.

Figure 20. Scenario 2 schematic shunting operations diagram

Once inside, the train is loaded and unloaded. However, if the current modus operandi were applied, one of the original tracks and one of the new tracks would serve solely as holding tracks for waiting trains. This arrangement would necessitate additional shunting manoeuvres to reposition trains between operational and non-operational tracks that.

The introduction of bridge cranes would enable trains to be serviced on any track. Furthermore, with a larger yard reach stacker would be less efficient than tugs.

6.3.5.2 Proposed Operational Model

The proposed operational model explores the integration of automation and its potential impact, highlighting how automation enhances the seamless cooperation among its various components, which is essential for effective operation. Furthermore, autonomous equipment requires dedicated algorithms that consider its features while introducing a smart and optimized logic to take advantage of them.

In both scenarios, automating shunting operations centres on three key elements: fully autonomous multimodal locomotives, DAC, and autonomous gates.

Autonomous locomotives are advanced rail vehicles equipped with technologies designed to operate without human intervention. They can align, couple, and decouple railcars with exceptional precision, eliminating the need for manual adjustments. Equipped with sensors such as LiDAR, radar, and cameras, these locomotives can detect and respond to obstacles on the tracks, ensuring safe and continuous operations. By leveraging real-time data and advanced algorithms, autonomous locomotives navigate efficiently, reducing delays and congestion through optimized movement based on global operational logic.

Remote decoupling systems enable automatic separation of railcars, eliminating manual intervention. These systems use sensors and communication technologies for precise decoupling, enhancing safety and speed, and reducing turnaround times.

Autonomous gates facilitate train flow in and out of the terminal. Equipped with sensors and cameras, they automate access and security, reducing the need for human operators.

In **Scenario 1**, the introduction of these autonomous elements would impact most of the activities. Specifically:

- **Train splitting into two cuts:** the coupler allows train splitting without human intervention.
- **First cut preparation:** the coupler allows for end-of-train marker addition.
- **First cut movement** (from station to terminal): the locomotive positions itself, couples with the railcars, performs the break tests and moves autonomously to reach the terminal. Automated gate allows for train entrance management without the need for an in-loco human operator.
- **Locomotive returns to station:** the locomotive autonomously passes through the gates and returns to the station to proceed for the next stage of operations.
- **Second cut movement** (from station to terminal): similar to the first cut.
- **Train inspection:** autonomous gates are equipped with sensors to monitor the train while it passes.
- **Switching the two cuts:** after the loading operations are carried out, autonomous loco-tractors handles the cuts repositioning.
- **First cut movement** (from terminal to station): once the loading operations on both parts of the train are terminated, the movement of the first cut back to the station is handled by the locomotive, with gates ensuring seamless terminal exit.
- **Locomotive returns to terminal:** the locomotive autonomously returns to the terminal after completing its trip.
- **Second cut movement** (from terminal to station): similar to the first cut movement.
- **Train reassembling:** the final reassembly is facilitated by the coupler.

Task	Autonomous Element		
	Locomotive	Coupler	Gate
Train Splitting into Two Cuts		X	
First Cut preparation	X	X	
First Cut Movimentation (station->terminal)	X	X	X
Locomotive Returns to Station	X		X
Second Cut Movimentation (station->terminal)	X	X	X
Train inspection			X
[Loading/Unloading the First Cut]			
Switch the Two Cuts	X		
[Loading/Unloading the Second Cut]			
First Cut Movimentationl (terminal->station)	X	X	X
Locomotive Returns to Terminal	X		X
Second Cut Movimentationl (terminal->station)	X	X	X
Reassemble the Train		X	

Figure 21: Autonomous elements used in the UC3 tasks.

In **scenario 2**, the process is leaner, but automation is as pervasive. In particular:

- **Train movement (from station to terminal):** the locomotive positions itself, couples with the railcars, performs the break tests and moves autonomously to reach the terminal. Automated gate allows for train entrance management without the need for an in-loco human operator.
- **Train inspection:** autonomous gates are equipped with sensors to monitor the train while it passes.
- **Train movement (from terminal to station):** once the loading operations on both parts of the train are terminated, the movement of the first cut back to the station is handled by the locomotive, with gates ensuring seamless terminal exit.

Task	Autonomous Element		
	Locomotive	Coupler	Gate
Train Movimentation (station -> terminal)	x	x	x
Train inspection			x
[Train Loading/Unloading]			
Additional Maneuvers to Discard a Railcar [Possible]	x	x	
Train Movimentation (terminal -> station)	x	x	x

Figure 22: Autonomous Elements used in the UC3 tasks II

Since the process is considered in its entirety, loading and unloading operations cannot be overlooked. These activities and their automation are of particular interest in the second scenario, where larger infrastructure necessitates the introduction of new equipment and process. Specifically, by implementing automated systems such as bridge cranes and automated guided vehicles (AGVs), the model aims to address current safety challenges while significantly enhancing operational performance. The use of automated bridge cranes allows trains to be serviced on any track, minimizing congestion and reducing the risk of accidents associated with manual loading and unloading processes.

Expected key impacts of integrating automation include:

Autonomous locomotive:

- **Enhanced safety:** eliminates human error, minimizes the risk of collisions, and reduces human exposure to hazardous conditions, such as extreme weather.
- **Precise control of operations:** automates critical tasks like braking, accelerating, and track switching, ensuring safer and more efficient shunting operations while preventing over-speeding and misjudged movements.
- **Increased operational efficiency:** achieved through optimized movements, reducing delays, congestion, and downtime.
- **Real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance:** ensures early detection of issues, contributing to smoother operations and reducing the risk of unplanned disruptions.

DAC:

- **Enhanced safety:** eliminates physical interaction during coupling and decoupling, reducing the risk of injuries and accidents.
- **Real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance:** continuous monitoring of pressure levels in the coupling systems for improved safety and predictive maintenance. For instance, it reduces the risk of high-pressure failures.

Gates:

- **Enhanced safety:** reduces human exposure to hazardous environments, decreasing the risk of injuries.
- Optimized traffic flow at the terminal.
- **Precise data availability and tracking:** automation requires and provides precise and reliable information on the location of equipment and containers.
- **Smooth cooperation and optimization:** the collaboration between shunting operation, loading and yard operations is essential for automated systems to function effectively. This integration fosters seamless interaction among different elements of the process and allows the global optimization of the system.

Environmental benefits: With more efficient operations, energy consumption will be optimised, reducing the carbon footprint associated with freight transport.

6.3.5.3 Data Flows and Interactions

Set parameters:

- **Layout specifications:** this includes both internal and external terminal designs. It details the number of tracks, their lengths, and relative positions within the terminal. It also encompasses the configuration and characteristics of the track that connects the terminal to the national network.
- **Fixed equipment:** the types of equipment that are permanently available for operations, such as locomotives.
- **Flow type:** the type of flow through the terminal including road2rail and rail2road traffic.
- **Schedules**

6.4 UC4 : Automated multimodal terminal operations

6.4.1 Use Case definition

6.4.1.1 Purpose and Scope

The objective of this use case is to employ a simulation model to evaluate the impact of a new automated intermodal terminal design, featuring the Autonomous Wagon Train (AWT) concept to improve cargo movement between different transport modes, on the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH. Terminals require faster, more seamless cargo transfers between rail, road, and sea transport to keep up with growing logistics demands. By allowing autonomous wagons to directly interact with ASCs, the automation not only enhances operational efficiency but also paves the way for smarter, more sustainable intermodal terminal operations. This system represents a leap forward in logistics technology, promising substantial improvements in speed, cost, and safety for container terminals. The simulation will take current traffic conditions as input to assess the effectiveness of this innovative approach.

By leveraging a simulation and modelling of the terminal's operations this project aims to:

- Improving the cargo moving between modes using ASC and AWG concept.

- Creating a terminal model to simulate the intramodality.
- Improve decision-making processes through predictive analytics and scenario planning, allowing terminal managers to visualize and quantify the benefits of automation before actual implementation.
- Enhance sustainability by optimizing yard operations to decrease machine run times and emissions.

The scope of this use case consists of the following components:

- **Autonomous Wagon Train (AWT):** Define and develop the concept of autonomous wagon train system in a minimal possible way matching the characteristics of NTB terminal.
- **Design a yard layout by adapting the AWT concept:** To make use of this concept, we need to redesign the yard layout. This design is not meant to be optimized. The integration to the terminal is intended.
- **Model Development:** Building an accurate and dynamic digital model of the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH that can simulate current and proposed terminal operations.
- **Input and Data Collection:** Gathering and integrating historical data on current traffic conditions, yard layouts, rail layout and operational workflows to provide inputs for the Digital Twin models.
- **Layout Design, configuration, and testing:** Designing and testing current and new automated layouts within the Digital Twin environment to analyse their behaviour.
- **Traffic Scenario Analysis:** Conducting simulations under various traffic scenarios to evaluate the potential impacts of each automated layout on terminal operations.
- **Performance Metrics:** Defining and measuring KPIs such as turnaround times, equipment utilization rates, and operational costs to assess improvements over the current layout.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involving terminal management, operational staff, and technology providers in the testing and validation process to ensure the proposed solutions meet practical and strategic needs.

6.4.1.2 General Overview of the Use Case

The UC4 aims to provide an overview of the impact of applying innovative automation technologies on the operational efficiency of the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven GmbH. To achieve this, simulation models will be used with two terminal designs, considering combinations of alternative traffic flows.

In more detail, Digital Twin models will be developed to simulate the current and alternative terminal operations. The current terminal uses manual straddle carriers and manual RTG for rails. The new automated one uses automated stacking cranes (ASC) with a new concept of autonomous wagon trains (AWT). In an AWT, wagons are electrically powered and are able to be detached from other wagons and move to the intended yard blocks to be loaded or discharged by ASC on the yard. In this scenario there is no need to use an intermediate equipment such as Reach Stackers (RS) since the wagons are able to move in the yard terminal. The yard design should be altered to adapt to this new concept. The coordination between ASCs, AGVs and autonomous wagons are controlled by the simulation models. To evaluate the effect of this new automated concept into the terminal, simulation models will be tested with different traffic conditions that an intermodal terminal may face. The optimization is not the main goal of this use case and can be assessed later. Additionally, it will provide input on the requirements for implementing yard

automation technologies to optimize the efficiency of the terminal's multimodal operations, enhance sustainability, and reduce the terminal's environmental footprint.

6.4.2 State-of-the-Art analysis of automated multimodal terminal operations

Multimodal terminal operations are very relevant and present in the logistics and transportation sectors, with a clear objective of transferring the cargos between different modes of transport, such as rail, road, air, and sea. This type of terminals serves as pillar hubs with the integration of different transportation networks, allowing a more efficient and effective movement of cargo from origin to destination.

The point of this type of terminals lies in their capability of optimizing supply chains, reducing transit times and also reducing all the costs associated with the transportation. Providing a centralized and common location for handling different types of freight, the multimodal terminals improve the flexibility and responsiveness in logistics operations. This point is crucial and aligned with the nowadays importance of fast-paced global economy, where the timeliness of deliveries and the efficient resource management are essential in order to have competitive advantage.

The automation in this type of terminals is also important and is emerging as the technology advances and can encompass different aspects, including cargo handling, traffic management, and communication systems, which all together will contribute to a more agile and productive terminal environment (Schwede & Wimmer, 2021).

Regarding all this, as the demand for the integrated logistic zones continues to rise, the evolution of automated multimodal terminal operations represents a key aspect in the context of ports; to increase the efficiency, sustainability and service quality of them. Adopting innovative technologies and practices, the stakeholders of the sector can optimize the operations and solve the challenges of this complicated and long change (Vacca et al. 2007).

The process of multimodal terminal operations involves several interconnected phases, each of them being relevant to ensure the correct operation of them. This is a visual representation of them:

Figure 23: Multimodal terminal operations Phases diagram

Here below you will find a detailed list of all the phases involved in automated multimodal terminal operations:

Phase	Description
Arrival of Cargo	The process starts with the arrival of cargo at the terminal. This arrival can come from different transportation modes (trucks, ships, or trains). At this point the arrival is notified and communicated to the terminal personnel to start on preparing the unloading.
Unloading and Inspection	Just after the arrival, the cargo is unloaded from its respective transport. Here, automated systems may enter in the process and assist in this phase to enhance efficiency and speed. Each shipment is inspected for any damage and also the documentation is reviewed to ensure accuracy in the cargo handling process.
Assessment and Planning	After unloading, terminal operators assess the incoming cargo and determine the best plan for its transportation to the next place. This phase involves analysing the requirements for each shipment, including destination, handling needs, and timing.
Storage and Handling	Once assessed, the cargo is either stored temporarily within the terminal or quickly prepared for immediate transfer to another transport mode (for example if the cargo comes from a boat can be immediately prepared to send it to a train). Automated storage systems may be used to manage inventory efficiently, ensuring that goods are accessible for quick retrieval.
Resource Allocation	This phase involves assigning the necessary resources, such as vehicles and equipment, for the subsequent movements of the cargo. It is a critical point in order to minimize delays and optimize operations, particularly during peak periods.
Execution of Transfers	The actual transfer of cargo between different transport modes takes place in this phase. In this point technologies like Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and robotic systems may jump in the process and be used to transport goods across the terminal, facilitating quick and efficient movement between different loading zones.
Monitoring and Adjustments	Throughout the transfer process, real-time monitoring systems have to track continuously the status of cargo movements and resource utilization. If any issues appear, adjustments can be made quickly to address delays or operational challenges, ensuring a good flow of operations.
Completion of Transfer Tasks	After cargo has been successfully transferred to the next transport mode, the completion of tasks is verified through automated reporting systems. This ensures that all movements are accurately documented and legal, and that the cargo is on the good track for its next journey.
Departure of Cargo	The final phase involves the departure of cargo from the terminal. Departure management systems coordinate the scheduling and departure of the next vehicles, ensuring that the cargo leave the terminal on time and in compliance with transportation regulations.

Additional Phases	Description
Data analysis and Reporting	In order to analyse the process, as the cargo leaves the port, data from the entire process is analysed to evaluate performance metrics, identify areas for improvement, and inform future operational strategies. This analysis helps in optimizing processes and improving the methods used.
Feedback Loop	A compilation of feedback and insights obtained from the last phase should be used and incorporated into the terminals processes for the continuous improvement. The stake holders must use it, to refine their strategies, implement or improve the innovative technologies and adapt to the real necessities of the terminal.

Table 22: Automated multimodal terminal operations Phases

6.4.2.1 Current Technology state

In this section, you will be able to find a comprehensive analysis of the current technology state in the context of the multimodal terminal operations.

As was mentioned before, the use of new and innovative technologies in the context of this type of terminals is increasing in a very fast way. The use of technology in multimodal terminal operations is not only improving the operational aspects and performance, but also improves the safety (by minimizing the human error and reducing the risks associated with the manual tasks). Including this type of technologies, stakeholders can create a more agile and responsible environment.

In the table below, we will delve deeper into the technologies used in each of the phases (defined before in this document) of a multimodal terminal operation context:

Arrival of Cargo	
Automatic Arrival Notification Systems	<u>Description:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Unloading and Inspection	
Automated Unloading Systems	<u>Description:</u> This type of technologies includes robotic arms and conveyor belts, which facilitate the rapid unloading of the cargo from transport vehicles.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used in ports and freight terminals to reduce manual labour and accelerate the unloading process.
Cargo Inspection Systems	<u>Description:</u> Automated systems that use scanning and imaging technologies (like X-ray and infrared) to inspect cargo for damage or security threats.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Implemented in terminals to ensure compliance with safety regulations and facilitate customs inspections, while maintaining security standards.
Assessment and Planning	
Cargo Management Software	<u>Description:</u> Software platforms that analyse incoming cargo and develop efficient plans for its next transportation.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used nowadays by terminal operators to optimize loading schedules and resource allocation.
	<u>Description:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies

Traffic Management Systems (TMS)	Current Applications: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Storage and Handling	
Automated Storage and Retrieval Systems (AS/RS)	<u>Description:</u> Systems that employ automated cranes and shuttles to store and retrieve cargo in an autonomous way, maximizing space utilization.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used in terminals and also in warehouses to speed up inventory management and improve the speed of cargo handling.
Mobile Robots	<u>Description:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Resource Allocation	
Resource Management Systems	<u>Description:</u> Software solutions that are used to track and allocate resources such as vehicles, personnel, and equipment to optimize operational efficiency.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used in multimodal terminals to enhance resource allocation during peak times and improve overall operational productivity.
Predictive Analytic Tools	<u>Description:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Execution of transfers	
Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)	<u>Description:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Robotic Loading Systems	<u>Description:</u> Automated systems designed to handle the loading of cargo to different types of transport (trucks, trains, or ships), reducing manual intervention.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Used in logistics operations to increase loading speed and accuracy, minimizing the risk of errors and injuries.
Digital Automatic Coupling (DAC)	<u>Description:</u> See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> While primarily applied in marshalling yards for train assembly and reconfiguration, DAC is also being explored in intermodal terminals context for its potential (for example to streamline the coupling and decoupling processes between wagons).
Autonomous wagon trains (AWT)	<u>Description:</u> This rail wagons are equipped with advanced autonomous systems, allowing them to move in an independence mode within terminal yards or intermodal terminals. The technology uses a combination of IoT sensors, GPS, and AI algorithms.
	<u>Current Applications:</u> AWTs are currently being tested in controlled environments and pilots projects all around the world (specially in Asia). It is still a low TRL technology for the moment, but successful trials have demonstrated its potential to reduce dependency on locomotives for short-distance movements, optimize yard spaces, and decrease operational delays,
Monitoring and Adjustments	
Real-Time Monitoring Systems	<u>Description:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Data Analytics Platforms	<u>Description:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	<u>Current Applications:</u> Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Completion of Transfer Tasks	

Task Verification Systems	Description: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	Current Applications: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Automated Reporting Tools	Description: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	Current Applications: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Departure of Cargo	
Departure Management Systems	Description: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	Current Applications: Implemented in intermodal terminals to coordinate logistics and improve the reliability of cargo transport.
Integrated Communication Systems	Description: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	Current Applications: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Data Analysis and Reporting	
Business Intelligence Tools	Description: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
	Current Applications: See Table 18: Shunting phases technologies
Feedback Loop for Continuous Improvement	
Feedback Management Systems	Description: Platforms that collect insights and data from terminal operations to inform future improvements and strategies (Bierwirth & Mesel, 2015).
	Current Applications: Used to enhance operational practices by allowing stakeholders to adapt based on performance feedback and evolving market demands.

Table 23: Automated multimodal terminal operations Phases Technologies

6.4.2.2 Case Studies

In this section, we will define and detail two real-world examples of automated multimodal terminal operations. These case studies highlight successful implementations of some of the advanced technologies mentioned earlier, and the positive outcomes achieved in terms of efficiency, safety, and overall performance.

→ [Case Study 1 Long Beach Container Terminal \(LBCT\), Port of Los Angeles \(USA\)](#)

Description of the Terminal: Long Beach Container Terminal is one of North America’s most advanced intermodal terminals. The terminal combines both port and rial operations, using advanced technologies like Digital Twins (very interesting and relevant for our AutoMoTIF project) and automation in cranes and transport systems. It is one of the most interesting terminals, in terms of minimizing the environmental impact versus improving the operational capacity.

LBCT uses also autonomous control systems (described in this document) in order to coordinate container movements between vessels, trains and trucks; with an interesting infrastructure design for the fast adaptation to the changing demands.

Key Technologies Used:

- Digital Twin
- Automated Cranes

- IoT Integration

Relevance to the Project: This Case Study illustrates in a good and interesting way how digitalization, Digital Twins, and automation can be integrated together to manage and achieve complex operations in multimodal terminals.

The scalability potential of the Case Study makes it an ideal example for the AutoMoTIF project.

→ [Case Study 2: Jebel Ali Terminal \(Dubai, UAE\)](#)

Description of the Terminal: The Jebel Ali Terminal, which is operated by DP World, is a terminal situated in a very concurred and strategic location; and is used as a connection point between Asia, Europe and Africa.

Jebel Ali is recognized as one of the most advanced terminals in the integration of the automation technologies and digital platforms in intermodal operations context. The terminal handles and transport a very high cargo volumes using automated cranes and digital management systems, making it a good model to follow for all the logistical management side.

Key Technologies Used:

- Automated Stacking Cranes (AutoSCs)
- IoT Platforms
- Artificial Intelligence (IA): Used for optimizing the resources allocation and for predicting and monitoring possible bottlenecks and logistic problems and delays, using the advanced analytics.

Relevance to the Project: Jebel Ali is a perfect example for the AutoMoTIF partners to be a reference in managing a complex intermodal terminal operation with a very strong technological implementation and integration.

Its advanced IoT and AI technologies and solutions used in this terminal, also provides a clear model for implementing this type of disruptive technologies in a multimodal terminal.

→ [Case Study 3: Maasvlakte II Terminal, Port of Rotterdam \(Netherlands\)](#)

Description of the Terminal: The Maasvlakte II Terminal, which is operated by APM Terminals, is one of the Europe's most advanced ports if we are talking about handling very large volumes of cargo, with a strong implementation of automation new technologies.

It is a unique terminal full electrical, so it has a strong focus regarding the sustainability (also for this point is an interesting example for AutoMoTIF).

This multimodal terminal (which is using autonomous vehicles and automated cranes) usually works only with containers; so, it is relevant for this type of cargo. The terminal is connected to the rest of Europe through a network of rail and barge transport, making it a ideal example of intermodal efficiency,

Key Technologies Used (all only applicated at containers cargo):

- Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)
- Automated Rubber-Tyred Gantred Cranes (ARTGs)
- Terminal Operating System (TOS)

Relevance to the Project: This case is fully interesting for AutoMoTIF project as it demonstrates how full (or mostly full) automation combined with digital tool can transform and improve the management of multimodal terminals.

The implementation of AGVs and automated cranes at this terminal, provides a clear model for increasing operational efficiency and reducing the emissions, aligning perfectly with AutoMoTIF's objectives.

→ [Case Study 4: “OPTIYARD” Project](#)

Project goal: The OptiYard project tried to improve the efficiency and performance of multimodal terminal operation, especially focused on rail freight terminals by optimizing real-time yard and network operations (as is reflected in the Use Case 3). The main goal is to improve the decision-making capabilities within marshalling yards by integrating advanced simulation tools, real-time data management, and optimization algorithms.

Description of the terminal: The project examines different European multimodal terminals and rail freight terminals, focusing on their infrastructure and operational complexities.

These terminals include a variety of marshalling yards and intermodal facilities that handle diverse types of traffic, vehicles and cargo.

Solution approach: Railway yards manage a multitude of complex and time-critical operations. Some of the main tasks included in the simulation of the project are:

- The reception of arrival trains
- Shunting and marshalling
- Dispatch of departing trains
- Management of locomotives and personnel.

The function specification for yards included three parts: the basic information of the yard activities, the yard simulation model and the yard management activities. The yard activity information specifies the basic characteristics of different activities conducted in yards, the yard simulation model simulates the activities and processes in yards, and the yard management model manages the progress of activities and processes.

Figure 24: Diagram of function specifications for yards

OptiYard’s approach focuses on developing real-time decision support systems that can monitor and optimize yard operations. This is achieved through:

- Villon Simulation Tool: A real-time simulation environment that models yard operations, including train sorting, marshalling, and shunting. The tool simulates various operational scenarios to optimize resource allocation and train movements.
- Real-time Data Integration: The project integrates real-time data from rail traffic management systems to improve the accuracy of yard operation models. This data is used to support dynamic decision-making, ensuring that yard operations are responsive to changes in train schedules and network conditions.
- Optimization Algorithms: Advanced algorithms are applied to optimize processes such as wagon sorting, scheduling, and the deployment of locomotives, reducing delays and improving overall yard efficiency.

Results: The results of the OptiYard project demonstrated the potential benefits of real-time optimization for rail freight yards. The use of simulation tools and optimization algorithms led to improved resource utilization, reduced train dwell times, and more efficient shunting operations. Key findings include:

- A significant reduction in delays, allowing for smoother train movements within and around the yard.
- Increased efficiency in sorting and shunting processes, maximizing the throughput of the terminal.
- Insights into the integration of real-time data, highlighting the potential for further improvements in yard management through enhanced data-sharing between rail operators and terminals.

→ Others

Port	Description of the case study
Port of Hamburg (Germany)	<p>Overview: The Port of Hamburg has adopted various automated solutions to streamline its multimodal terminal operations.</p> <p>Technologies Used: Automated storage and retrieval systems (AS/RS), real-time monitoring systems, and predictive analytics.</p> <p>Results: The integration of automation has led to improved resource utilization and reduced idle times for cargo handling. Enhanced visibility into operations has allowed for quicker adjustments to workflows, resulting in a more responsive and efficient terminal environment.</p>
Port of Antwerp (Belgium)	<p>Overview: The Port of Antwerp has invested heavily in automation to enhance its multimodal operations.</p> <p>Technologies Used: Automated traffic management systems, Digital Twin technology, and advanced data analytics tools.</p> <p>Results: These technologies have improved the port's ability to manage the flow of goods efficiently, leading to reduced congestion and quicker turnaround times. The implementation of Digital Twins has enabled better forecasting and resource management, optimizing overall terminal performance.</p>
DP World Jebel Ali, United Arab Emirates	<p>Overview: DP World's Jebel Ali Port is one of the busiest ports globally, known for its advanced automation initiatives.</p> <p>Technologies Used: Automated quay cranes, AGVs, and terminal operating systems.</p> <p>Results: The automation of loading and unloading processes has dramatically increased efficiency, with the port achieving a significant reduction in container dwell times. This improvement has strengthened its position as a leading global trade hub.</p>

Table 24: Case Studies, Use Case 4

6.4.3 User needs and technological gaps

This section will delve into the specific user needs associated with the multimodal terminal operations, as well as the technological gaps that must be addressed to improve the performance and drive progress in the sector.

The section has been constructed with the feedback and the insights of the project partners implicated in this Use Case, some external experts and with certificated information reviewed. The following key user needs have been identified:

User need	Information
Operational needs	

<p>Efficient Cargo Transfer Between Modes</p>	<p>Description: The terminals needs to be more speedy , more seamless cargo transfers between rail, road, and sea transport to keep up with growing logistics demands.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Automation tools used for achieve this need are robotic cranes, Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs), and smart conveyor systems. This type of technologies are necessary to improve speed and reduce human error in handling transfers in the context of automation.</p>
<p>Flexibility in Cargo Management</p>	<p>Description: A critical point under the umbrella of automation this type of terminals is to be ready for the diferent cargo types and volumes which can vary significantly, requiring flexible systems that can handle different cargo sizes, shapes, and types (containerized, bulk, intermodal).</p> <p>Need for solutions: Terminals need modular, adaptable systems like smart cargo sorting algorithms and versatile robotic systems to accommodate a variety of cargo efficiently.</p>
<p>Predictive Maintenance for Equipment</p>	<p>Description: Frequent use of traditional and also innovative automation machinery requires constant maintenance, and unplanned breakdowns can detain the flow operations. Incorporation predicitive tools for the maintanance is a critical point to address.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Integration of IoT sensors for predictive maintenance, allowing equipment to be monitored in real time, reducing the likelihood of unexpected downtime.</p>
<p>Minimized Waiting Times for Vehicles</p>	<p>Description: Excessive waiting times for trucks, ships, or trains at the terminal can cause bottlenecks, reducing operational efficiency.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Implementing smart traffic and scheduling systems that dynamically adjust based on real-time data to reduce congestion and optimize flow.</p>
<p>Operational needs</p>	
<p>Accurate Real-Time Information</p>	<p>Description: Operators need access to up-to-date cargo and equipment status to make timely decisions, especially in high-volume terminals.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Advanced tracking systems integrated with IoT sensors that can provide real-time status updates on cargo location, condition, and equipment availability.</p>
<p>Increased Safety Standards</p>	<p>Description: With heavy machinery and high traffic, there is always a risk of accidents during operations, especially when multiple transport modes are involved.</p> <p>Need for solutions: Automated safety monitoring systems and real-time alerts can improve workplace safety by detecting hazards and ensuring compliance with safety protocols.</p>
<p>Environmental Sustainability</p>	<p>Description: Terminals need to reduce their carbon footprint as environmental regulations tighten (Acciaro & Wilmsmeier, 2018).</p>

	Need for solutions: Energy-efficient automated equipment (e.g., electric cranes), systems to minimize idle times, and intelligent energy management solutions are required to achieve sustainability goals.
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Table 25: User Needs, Use Case 4

While significant advancements have been made in multimodal terminal operations, various technological gaps still exist. Identifying these technological gaps is crucial for stakeholders seeking to enhance efficiency, safety, and reliability. The following **key gaps** have been identified:

Key gap	Information
Lack of Comprehensive Automation for Transfers	Description: Although parts of the cargo handling process (like loading/unloading) are automated, full automation across all stages—especially transfer between modes—remains incomplete. Impact: Partial automation leads to inefficiencies and increased operational costs. Fully automated systems could significantly enhance throughput and reduce errors.
Inadequate Data Integration Between Systems	Description: Data from different subsystems (like transport, cargo, and equipment management) often remains isolated, limiting overall visibility and decision-making capabilities. Impact: This disconnect can make it difficult the optimization of resource allocation and scheduling, leading to delays, and complicates the achievement of new opportunities for improvement.
Limited Infrastructure for Long Trains	Description: Many terminals, including multimodal hubs, are not equipped to handle longer trains (750 meters or more), which reduces operational efficiency. Impact: Without the infrastructure to accommodate longer trains, terminals face bottlenecks and are forced to split trains, which increases handling time and costs.
Lack of Standardized Interfaces Between Systems	Description: Many automated systems (e.g., cranes, AGVs, traffic management) operate independently, leading to inefficient coordination. Impact: This lack of interoperability slows down operations, as systems cannot communicate rapidly or share data (UNCTAD, 2021). Establishing standardized communication protocols would enable smoother coordination between systems.
Low Precision of Current Sensing Systems	Description: While sensing systems exist, many current solutions fight with environmental conditions (e.g., poor visibility, extreme weather), affecting precision. Impact: Inaccurate data from sensors leads to operational inefficiencies and safety risks. Higher-precision sensing systems are necessary for reliable automation in diverse weather conditions.

Table 26: Technological GAPS, Use Case 4

6.4.4 Use Case Scenarios

6.4.4.1 Scenario 1: Comparison between Current Terminal Layout and Adapted to the AWT

Narrative Description

The steps to be followed for the scenario are the following:

1. Design of the “as-is” partial Digital Twin reflecting today’s equipment and terminal model
2. Design of a partial Digital Twin with adapting AWT.
3. Simulation using different traffic flows (proportion between rail and truck) on both Digital Twins.
4. Result analysis with development of specific predefined KPIs

The following diagram shows the algorithm of the scenario execution:

Figure 25: Scenario execution

In this point it is important to describe and explain the AWT system design concept:

AWT Concept Overview:

The core idea is to integrate Autonomous Wagon Trains (AWTs) with intermodal terminals. These wagons are equipped with autonomous driving technologies that allow them to navigate the terminal independently,

moving directly to and from ASCs without the need for traditional Terminal Truck or Straddle Carrier or Reach Stacker. This direct interaction significantly improves the process of transferring containers between different transport modes such as ship, rail, and road by minimizing handling steps and equipment used.

Key Components of the System:

- **Autonomous Wagons:** Each wagon in the AWT is equipped with advanced navigation systems, including GPS, LiDAR, and perhaps AI-driven algorithms, which allow it to identify the optimal route within the yard and execute movements without human intervention.

Communication and Integration Systems: A high-level integration system ensures seamless communication between the wagons, ASCs, and the terminal's management system. This integration allows for real time adjustments to operations based on container arrival patterns, ASC availability, and other logistical parameters.

- **Safety and Monitoring Systems:** To safely integrate AWTs into busy terminal environments, robust safety systems must be in place. These could include collision avoidance systems, emergency stop mechanisms, and constant monitoring from a central control room.

Advantages:

Increased efficiency: By eliminating the need for additional handling equipment, containers can transition directly between transport modes, significantly reducing transfer times and enhancing throughput. Furthermore, this model enables synchronous operations between the rail and the yard. Each automated wagon can be unloaded and reloaded independently of the others, ensuring seamless and efficient handling.

- **Reduced costs:** Less equipment means reduced capital investment and maintenance costs, as well as lower operational costs due to decreased fuel use and fewer labor requirements.
- **Enhanced scalability:** The system can be scaled more easily, as adding more autonomous wagons or adjusting routes can accommodate fluctuating cargo volumes without significant disruptions.
- **Improved safety:** Minimizing human involvement in direct cargo handling can lead to safer work environments, as autonomous systems are less prone to operational errors associated with human fatigue.
- **Environmental benefits:** Autonomous electric wagons can help reduce the carbon footprint of terminal operations, aligning with global sustainability goals.

Implementation Challenges:

- **Technological complexity:** Developing and integrating sophisticated autonomous navigation systems within the existing terminal infrastructure will be challenging and require extensive testing.
- **Regulatory Hurdles:** Adapting current regulations to accommodate autonomous vehicles operating in dense, complex environments like container terminals may be time-consuming.
- **High Initial Investment:** While long-term cost savings are significant, the initial outlay for developing and implementing these autonomous systems can be substantial.
- **Change Management:** Transitioning to this new system will necessitate substantial adjustments to operational procedures and comprehensive personnel training. Alternative workforce utilization models should be developed to retain the terminal's workforce while simultaneously creating new, high-skilled positions.

Key Variables and Parameters

Some of the key variables and parameters needed for the scenario related to the current terminal model:

- The historical data.
- Terminal current layout.
- Container allocation rules and policies: when a container is going to be moved the source and destination location are clear, so in the simulation and modelling part this “positioning” decisions should be clear
- Vessel and train schedules, along with truck visit patterns (including peak times, average number of trucks per hour, and the distribution of truck traffic throughout the day).
- Terminal KPIs and metrics such as vessel/train/truck turn-around time, moves per hour, yard occupancy etc.
- The container handling equipment types and characteristics.
- The KPI definitions and formulas.

The key variables and parameters needed for the scenario related to the new terminal model:

- AWT behaviour and specification:
- Controlling rules
 - Movement specifications
 - Shunting rules
 - Attaching and detaching rules
 - Rail requirement
- Safety requirement
- Terminal design layout
- Rail passages within the yard
 - Rail trucks required for shunting and wagon rearrangement
 - ASC delivery point specification for wagons
 - Adaptation for trucks and AGV
- Automation rules
- Container allocation rules and policies
- Vessel and train schedules, along with truck visit patterns (including peak times, average number of trucks per hour, and the distribution of truck traffic throughout the day).
- Safety
- Shunting rules

The image below shows the conceptual new terminal design:

Figure 26: conceptual new terminal design using AWT

6.4.5 Concept of Operations (ConOps)

6.4.5.1 Current Operational Environment

The North Terminal Bremerhaven (NTB) covers over 1 million square meters and has a capacity exceeding 50,000 TEUs. NTB operates 18 ship-to-shore cranes alongside manned straddle carriers, which handle the horizontal transportation and stacking of containers in the yard. The straddle carrier yard at NTB is organized with blocks positioned perpendicular to the quay. In addition to quay operations, NTB operates a rail terminal with 6 rail tracks equipped with four transtainers for loading and unloading, where straddle carriers are also used for horizontal container transport. Finally, it should be noted that NTB has more than 2000 reefer plugs while it can accommodate approximately 1000 IMO containers.

6.4.5.2 Proposed Operational Model

The proposed operational concept for UC4 includes utilizing Automated Stacking Cranes (ASCs) with two different yard designs, where yard blocks are oriented either parallel or perpendicular to the quay. Shuttle carriers, which have both transportation and stacking capabilities, will be used for the horizontal movement of containers.

6.4.5.3 Data Flows and Interactions

The data flow for the use case is meticulously structured to ensure that each step within every scenario is clearly defined regarding its requirements and expected outputs. This level of detail is critical, as it fosters a comprehensive understanding of the interactions and dependencies across various stages of the

terminal's operational proposal. In this setup, the Digital Twin model plays a pivotal role. It not only simulates terminal operations but also serves as a framework for testing and refining the data flows across different terminal modules.

Digital Twin and Data Entity Design: The design of data entities and their integration into the partial Digital Twin model are foundational to defining how data flows throughout the terminal. This model reflects a partial yet substantial representation of the terminal's operational dynamics, allowing stakeholders to manipulate the operational impacts of different configurations and scenarios. The Digital Twin aids in the optimization of processes and in identifying potential bottlenecks before they impact real-world operations.

Current Data Model Utilization: As of now, the data model incorporates elements from the N4 data models, which are standard in current terminal operations. These models provide a robust foundation for managing straightforward entities such as Containers, Moves, and Vessel Visits. Their simplicity ensures reliability and ease of maintenance, facilitating smooth operations across common terminal activities.

Complexity in New System Components: However, the system expands significantly in complexity when integrating components like the Automated Stacking Cranes (ASCs) and the AWT. The ASC controllers, for example, require intricate data flows that accommodate real-time decision-making and synchronization with the terminal's overall traffic management system. Similarly, the AWT demands a sophisticated controlling logic to navigate autonomously within the terminal, interact with other equipment, and perform tasks such as loading and unloading without human intervention.

Controlling Logic and Data Integration: The controlling logic for the AWT involves advanced algorithms that process data from multiple sources, including real-time location data, container weight and destination data, and ASC availability. Integrating this data effectively requires high-performance computing solutions and real-time data processing capabilities. This integration is crucial for maintaining the flow of operations and ensuring that the terminal can handle the dynamic nature of shipping and logistics.

7 Conclusions

The main objective of this Deliverable was to explore and examine current and emerging technologies in maritime and rail terminals, identify the needs and gaps of the partners involved in the four use cases (See [Annex III: User needs and technological GAPS summary](#)), and define the foundations and scenarios for their automation (See sections ‘Use Case Scenarios’ and ‘Concept of Operations’ for each UC)) as well as a common Reference Architecture (See [Reference Architecture for Digital Twins](#)).

A comprehensive literature review was conducted on automated vessel calls, port operations, shunting train operations, and multimodal terminal operations, including a description of the process, current technologies and case studies for each of them.

For vessel call automation, the standard port call process is described, identifying the technologies involved in each phase, particularly during berthing, unberthing, and cargo operations. In automated port operations, the phases of Ro-Ro terminal operations are identified. This section also highlights the different levels of automation within terminals and emphasizes the importance of automating the storage and movement of Ro-Ro cargo. For automated shunting train operations, the shunting process is described, along with key technologies for each of the phases. Lastly, a mapping of phases and technologies in multimodal operations is presented, focusing on automation in communication and cargo movement between transport modes.

Regarding the technologies used in port and railway operations, it has been noted that, although full implementation is still progressing, some emerging technologies are already being adopted in major ports worldwide. These include Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), Machine Learning, and automated machinery in cargo and logistics operations, such as ARTGs, AGVs, and AutoSC (See [Emerging technologies](#)). These technologies are crucial for optimizing and enhancing terminal operations, addressing increasing global demand, and meeting the evolving needs of sector stakeholders. However, transitioning to automation in multimodal freight transport presents challenges (see [Challenges and barriers of automation in multimodal transport](#)), particularly in terms of investment and mitigating operational losses during shifts in processes and infrastructure. To address these challenges, Digital Twin technology emerges as a solution that simulates transactions and processes with real data, without affecting day-to-day operations. As explained in section 5.1 [Reference Architecture for Digital Twins](#), Digital Twin models can range from basic static versions that visually capture data to autonomous Digital Twins that predict, optimize, and control specific port operations.

Each use case definition outlines its scope, objectives, Concept of Operations (ConOps), and scenarios, providing a structured framework to investigate the potential benefits of automation in enhancing efficiency, safety, and sustainability.

UC1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels focuses on the automation of the port call process, with an emphasis on autonomous tugboats and Automated Mooring Systems. By simulating vessel arrivals, berthing, and departures under various conditions in a virtual port, the use case aims to identify the fundamental requirements for automation and its potential to improve operational efficiency and safety.

UC2 : Automated port operations investigates the application of automation in port terminal logistics, particularly in cargo handling and intra-terminal transport processes in the port of Bilbao. Simulations comparing baseline operations with automated scenarios are intended to reveal opportunities for improving turnaround times, reducing inefficiencies, and enhancing environmental performance, with scalability to diverse terminal contexts.

UC3 : Automated shunting as a Service oriented platform explores the implementation of autonomous technologies in an inland intermodal terminal (MIS). By simulating current and future configurations, the use case evaluates how automation can optimize rail freight processes, facilitate a shift to multimodal logistics, and address the evolving demands of intermodal freight transport.

UC4 : Automated multimodal terminal operations introduces the Autonomous Wagon Train (AWT) concept for the Northern Terminal Bremerhaven. Simulations of current and proposed layouts aim to assess the operational and environmental benefits of integrating automation, including more efficient cargo transfers, reduced reliance on intermediate equipment, and improved sustainability in terminal operations.

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9 Annexes

9.1 Annex I: Use Cases summary

Freight transport pillar	Use case
Automated vessel calls	UC1: Automated berthing/unberthing of freight vessels
Automated port operations	UC2: Automated port operations
Automated shunting	UC3: Automated Shunting as a Service oriented platform
Automated Rail terminal operation	UC4: Automated multimodal terminal operations

Table 27: Freight transport pillar - Use Case

9.2 Annex II: Partners interviewed

Partner	Role in AutoMoTIF
Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS)	UC1 Coordinators and developers
Telenavis (TEL)	UC1 Developers
Vicomtech (VICOM)	UC2 Developers
Port of Bilbao (BPL)	UC2 Pilot Site
Consignaciones Toro y Betolaza (CTyB)	UC2 End-User
Mosaic (MOS)	UC3 Developers
Magli Intermodal Service (MIS)	UC3 Pilote Site
Eurnex (ENX)	UC3 & 4 Railway Research Experts
Development & Innovation in Transport Systems (DITS)	UC4 Developers
North Sea Terminal Bremerhaven (NTB)	UC4 Pilot Site
Data and System Planning (DSP)	UC4 Developers
ALICE	Cross-cutting support
Gandolapp	External
Tenalach Consulting	External

Table 28: Interviewed partners for SoTA

9.3 Annex III: User needs and technological GAPS summary

User Needs

UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4
Automate berthing and unberthing process	Optimize and coordinate loading and unloading	Fast and Reliable Automated Coupling/Decoupling Systems	Efficient cargo transfer between modes
High level of connection (wireless) between vessel, tugboat and port	Material inspection	Precision in Wagon Positioning for Sequential Shunting Tasks	Flexibility in cargo management
Data exchange between towed vessel, tug and the port	Shunting operations	Reduction of Wagon Coupling and Decoupling Time	Predictive maintenance for equipment
Tugboats technologies	Cargo transfer	Energy Optimization During Automated Shunting Movements	Minimized waiting times for vehicles
(real time) Process monitoring by shore	Resource allocation	Efficient Track Allocation for High-Volume	Accurate real-time information
Safety management issues	Event scheduling	Optimized Resource Allocation	Increased safety standards
Tugboats allocation	Dynamic decision support	Real-Time Operational Overview	Environmental sustainability
-	Synchronization	Compliance with Automated Safety	

Table 29: Summary of User Needs for the four Cases

Technological Gaps:

UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4
Continuous process monitoring (unmanned tugs)	Monitoring	Automation Limitations	Lack of comprehensive automation for transfers
Interaction of autonomous tugboats with conventional vessels and tugboats	Software challenges	Interoperability Issues	Data integration

Data exchange rate and management	Data integration consistency and management	Data utilization challenges	Limited infrastructure for long trains
Cyber security issues	Infrastructure limitations	Scalability Concerns	Lack of standardized interfaces between systems
-	Demand forecasting	Limited Predictive Capabilities	Low precision of current sensing systems
-		Insufficient User Training Resources	

Table 30: Summary of Technological Gaps for the four Use Cases

9.4 Annex IV: Template interview

Annex IV: Template Interview

Name and Surname	
Position	
Company	
Interview Date	
Implication on AutoMoTIF (UC)	
Summary of key points	
Findings	

Table 31: Template interview

Context and purpose of the interview.

Current Use Case needs.

Current and future technologies for the automation of the transport.

Current and future technologies for the implementation of automation for multimodal implementation.

Challenges and barriers related to the implementation of automation.

Challenges and barriers related to the implementation of automation for multimodal implementation.

Case studies to include in the project.